

Comparative Evaluation of 2D COVID-19 Recognition Systems Using Chest CT Images

Lois Anne Leal

*Master of Science in
Computer Vision, Robotics, and Machine Learning*
from the
University of Surrey

Department of Electronic Engineering
Faculty of Engineering and Physical Sciences
University of Surrey
Guildford, Surrey, GU2 7XH, UK

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Supervised by: Miroslaw Bober, Ph.D.

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Lois Anne Leal

Author Signature

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Supervisor's name: Miroslaw Bober, Ph.D.

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ABSTRACT

A staggering number of studies heeded the call to apply AI in aiding the COVID-19 pandemic which leads us to ask: *Which system is better?* Reviews and appraisals have answered this by concluding that “none of the models identified are of potential clinical use” and are not directly comparable to each other. However, umbrella reviews show that these conclusions are limited by qualitative approaches and the broadness scope, and are susceptible to disagreements. On the other hand, quantitative approaches such as comparative analysis and generalizability studies were limited on self-trained models and are still scarce. We aim to answer this by conducting an empirical comparative evaluation of 2D COVID-19 binary classification systems using chest CT images. We further divided the task to single slice and multiple slice classification which differ in the number of slices that influences the prediction. Our evaluation is guided by the data and model characteristics along with the conflicts, specifically data leakage and frankenstein datasets. Among the 15 datasets and 13 models that are publicly available, we highlighted promising models: for Single Slice Classification, we have COVID-Net CT-2 S, COVID-Net CT-1 S [78], and Self-Trans [86]; and for Multiple Slice Classification, we have Deep Wilcoxon [96] and TAC - ResNet14 [97]. These models show either best performance in the leaderboard, detecting either of the classes well, being confidently right and not confidently wrong, or nearly calibrated. We also provided a global view of the models’ behavior using averaged Grad-CAM. Lastly, the worst performing models for both subtasks are the models trained in COVID-CTset data [79] which are susceptible to data mismatch and extreme outcomes.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CC-CCII	China Consortium of Chest CT Image Classification
Chest CT images	Chest Computed Tomography images
CNCB	China National Center for Bioinformation
COVID-19-NY-SBU	Stony Brook University COVID-19 Positive Cases
CXR	Chest X-Ray
DICOM (Image Format)	Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine
LIDC-IDRI	Lung Image Database Consortium (LIDC) - Image Database Resource Initiative (IDRI)
LUNA	LUnG Nodule Analysis
NiFTI (Image Format)	Neuroimaging Informatics Technology Initiative
NRRD (Image Format)	Nearly Raw Raster Data
STOIC	Study of thoracic CT in COVID-19
TCIA	The Cancer Imaging Initiative
TIF/TIFF (Image Format)	Tag Image File Format

1 INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) refers to the disease causing the pandemic as coronavirus disease (COVID-19) and the virus as severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) last 2020 [1]. As of early 2022, the total recorded confirmed cases was around 5.8 million with the numbers still increasing globally [2].

There are currently two ways of confirming the cases: by extracting nose and throat samples and by medical imaging. Methods involving extraction of samples are Reverse Transcription Polymerase Chain Reaction (RT-PCR), lateral flow test, and antigen where RT-PCR is the gold standard. However, RT-PCR takes time to report the results, may not be available in other places or even have inconclusive results. The second set of methods which involves medical imaging is usually in the form of chest computed tomography (CT), chest x-rays (CXR) and lung ultrasound [3-4]. Medical practitioners and the like have debated the usefulness of medical imaging in detecting COVID-19. Recent studies show that medical imaging does serve as a complementary tool of confirmation or as an alternative in cases where the methods involving the extraction of samples are not possible. It is also seen that medical imaging given the long established imaging machines, provide faster results and that the raw images can be preserved. Among the three, chest CT is considered the gold standard, recommended as one of the primary tools for diagnosis, and comparable to RT-PCR while CXR and ultrasound can be leveraged in certain situations [5-7].

Given the continuous rise of infections, long queues in testing centers and lack of staff (with the few initial numbers also getting infected themselves) are two major challenges which stretched the healthcare systems. These challenges and the opportunity of rapidly increasing amounts of data call for numerous developers and medical practitioners to employ artificial intelligence (AI) in conducting studies and developing tools to aid healthcare systems for the efficient and safe detection of COVID-19.

1.1 Background and Context

The call for AI systems has been heeded positively by the community as seen in competitions such as in Kaggle [8], International Conference on Image Analysis and Processing (ICIAP) [9], International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV) [10], and European Conference on Computer Vision (ECCV) [11]. Around 237,000 papers were also published with the numbers still continuing to rise [12].

The staggering amount of works being published resulted in the need for critical evaluations and reviews to enable researchers to have a better grasp of the situation and provide insights that will improve future studies. With performance being reported as high as 1.00 given the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) performance metric [13], it is surprising that the

common conclusions in the reviews published in the last two years narrowed down to telling that all published works were problematic—none of them are deemed usable and the performance of each system cannot be directly compared to each other given the varying setups. Thus, these reviews recommended various improvements and further called for continuous rigorous reviews of future works [13-15].

Most of these reviews used qualitative approaches. For reporting, most used Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) [16] and Transparent reporting of a multivariable prediction model for individual prognosis or diagnosis (TRIPOD) [17] while others followed a freestyle review. Data extraction guidelines such as Critical Appraisal and Data Extraction for Systematic Reviews of Prediction Modelling Studies (CHARMS) [18] and Prediction model Risk Of Bias ASsessment Tool (PROBAST) [19] for risk of bias were also used. For studies focused on medical imaging, they used CheckList for Artificial Intelligence in Medical imaging (CLAIM) [20] for assessing deep learning papers, and Radiomic Quality Score (RQS) [21] for assessing traditional machine learning papers. Other reviews had their own methodologies utilized.

Along with the increasing volume of work comes with the increasing number of reviews. [12] provided the 2022 umbrella review of 22 published reviews focusing on using AI techniques for detecting COVID-19 using medical images. They used PRISMA for Diagnostic Test Accuracy (PRISMA-DTA) [22] and A Measurement Tool to Assess Systematic Reviews (AMSTAR 2) [23] for the assessment. Some of their conclusions include the broadness of the reviews which impedes deeper analysis and evident multiple disagreements.

These works show the need for the continuous evaluation of existing works, to conduct an in-depth analysis and the need to shed perspectives on the conclusions and disagreements between reviews and works, not in a qualitative approach, but by conducting experimentations on the existing datasets and models themselves.

Different works did focus on quantitative approaches such as comparative analysis and generalizability studies; however, they did not enable direct comparison of existing studies, instead, most of the setups focused on the analysis of various deep learning architectures on one dataset (independent or combination of existing datasets), some trained one model to test on at most four independent datasets to understand generalizability and some measured models against radiologists [31-38]. Nonetheless, generalizability studies for diagnosing COVID-19 using chest CT images are still scarce.

Given these, this study aims to provide an in-depth analysis by focusing COVID-19 image recognition systems using chest CT, to enable direct comparison of existing studies by experimenting on the datasets and models themselves, and to generate conclusions with empirical basis which may or may not agree with the previous conclusions.

1.2 Objectives

This study has the following objectives:

- Perform critical literature review
- Select, replicate, and analyze existing CT image datasets and binary classification models
- Conduct a comparative evaluation across publicly available datasets and models to understand the performance of existing works and to generate conclusions with empirical basis
- Show the features which the models have learned

1.3 Achievements

The main achievements to date cover the following:

- Synthesized the significance and contribution of the study given the thousands of already existing studies about COVID-19
- Explored the role of chest CT images in diagnosing the disease
- Introduced two subtasks: Single and Multiple Slice Classification
- Analyzed and comparatively evaluated 15 datasets and 13 models involving the leaderboard approach and beyond in the presence of data-model conflicts
- Discussed the issues of data mismatch, data leakage, and changes between the internal and external rankings
- Highlighted promising and worst works

1.4 Overview of Dissertation

Background Theory and Literature Review. The sections found in this part justifies the use of chest CT images for detecting COVID-19 in the clinical perspective; compares its role against other available methods such as RT-PCR, CXR, and lung ultrasound; provides an overview of existing reviews and appraisals where we also elaborate their methodologies and conclusions on the strengths and weaknesses of existing works and their further recommendations; explores an umbrella review and studies which show the limitation of the reviews and example disagreements on the conclusions; show the existing quantitative approaches such as comparative analysis and generalizability studies; and finally, the summary of the section. This part is significant to show the reader an overview of data, how it is being used, the challenges in using it and the gaps that this study fills.

Materials and Methods. This chapter is divided into five sections: dataset and model collection, single vs. multiple slice classification, single slice classification, multiple slice classification, and evaluation methodology. The first part reasons regarding the collection of the datasets and models that are considered in this study. We then organized these works into the two types of image slices—single and multiple slices. In both categories, we dive deeper to the datasets and models under them—covering their characteristics, conflicts, and challenges in reproducibility along with the

necessary modifications. This section presents the bulk of this chapter since it will provide perspectives on the validity of the conclusions that can be made. Lastly, we provide an overview of the evaluation methodology used for the results and discussion in the next section.

Results and Discussions. This is broken down into three main parts—the first two covers the results for both single slice classification and multiple slice classification, and the last one is the general discussions. For the first two parts, we cover the leaderboard approach which uses the evaluation metrics—Accuracy, AUC, weighted F1-Score, and weighted Precision—to see where each model stand against the others given with or without the lens of the conflicts; and beyond the leaderboard approach which covers the modified confusion matrix, confidence distribution, model calibration, and saliency maps. Other supplemental results can be found in *Appendix*. In the general discussions, we discuss the takeaways we got from both setups and highlight the best and worst performing models in this study.

Conclusion. The conclusion covers the evaluation and future works. With evaluation, we looked back at what has been covered and highlighted the contributions of this work. For future works, we envision four significant and broad areas of studies namely: the effect of different image representations on modern neural networks, application of model calibration techniques, further investigation of the multiple slice classification subtask, and lastly, the investigation and approaches to distribution shifts.

2 BACKGROUND THEORY AND LITERATURE REVIEW

In this section, we will be looking at three main topics: the use of CT images for detecting COVID-19; the reviews and the appraisals with their limitations and disagreements; and the existing comparative analysis and generalization studies. This will help us position our work in contrast with current works.

As we will be focusing on chest CT images, it is important to justify its use on detecting COVID-19 as different tools have their own strengths and weaknesses which dictates its appropriate usage. First is an overview of what it is and the possible file formats the images are saved. We will also look at its own capabilities of detecting COVID-19 such as the evidence of COVID-19 features that can be found. We will also give an overview of the perspectives from different medical authorities regarding its use. After that, we compare it with RT-PCR and other medical imaging such as CXR and lung ultrasound to understand its position against these methods from a clinical perspective.

Second, we discuss the reviews and appraisals of using artificial intelligence to detect COVID-19, where we emphasize their methodology and conclusions which focus on the strengths, weaknesses and recommendations regarding the existing works. This will not only give us an overview of what is happening and where the current problems in the existing works occur but also a view of the impact of their review methodology on coming down to these conclusions which connects it to the next part. The third part talks about the limitations and example disagreements on the conclusions, in which we may anticipate that our results later on may or may not agree with.

Lastly, after looking at qualitative approaches, we look if there are existing quantitative approaches that are close to what we want to do. Most of these studies we found are in the form of comparative analysis and generalizability studies. Here we understand the experiment setups and the conclusions that they made from those.

2.1 Use of Chest CT Images for Detecting COVID-19 (Clinical Context)

2.1.1 Justification of Usage

Computed Tomography (CT) images of the chest are created with the use of x-ray and computing technology. It allows taking a cross-sectional view of the lungs which are saved as “slices”. This imaging technology provides more details than the common chest x-ray [32-33]. Medical images such as CT are usually stored in Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) format which contains information such as the header containing the metadata (e.g. demographics, study parameters) and the image data. In clinical practice, they usually remove specific metadata to follow data privacy guidelines before transmitting it for research and educational purposes. Other formats that radiologists encounter are those that have lossless compression such as TIF/TIFF, GIF, and PNG

and lossy formats such as JPEG and its variants [34]. Fig 2.2 shows the usual usage of the formats. It is also argued that there are cases where uncompressed images consume much storage when in fact radiologists will only analyze some parts of it for interpretation [34]. Specifically for detecting COVID-19, a senior radiologist from Wuhan, China who has been working for the pandemic has agreed that even if high resolution images are preferable, lossy compression or sub-optimal images can still be used by medical practitioners to diagnose COVID-19 [35].

Table 2.1: Advantages, disadvantages, and applications in clinical radiology of different image formats. Adapted from [34]

Figure 2.1: Illustration of capturing a chest CT scan image from a patient. Adapted from [33]

File format	Advantages	Disadvantages	Applications in clinical radiology
JPEG (.jpg)	Permits setting compression level; small image size	Low image quality at higher degrees of compression	Images for on-screen display (websites and PowerPoint® presentations)
GIF (.gif)	Good internet browser support; good for displaying animations	Larger file sizes; limited color support (256 colors or 256 shades of gray)	Images for display on a website
PNG (.png)	Good internet browser support; good image quality	Limited acceptance with earlier web browsers	Teaching files; publication; images for display on a website
TIFF (.tif)	High image quality	Large file size	Master copies of teaching file; format preferred by journals for publication

Scientifically, the use of chest CT images can be justified since COVID-19 leaves recognizable features in the scans [36-40]. Ground glass opacities (GGO), consolidation, reticular pattern, and crazy paving patterns interlobular septal thickening, bilateral distribution and subsegmental vessel enlargements are some of the typical features found in different observational studies while pleural effusions, nodules, and multifocal pneumonia are examples for atypical features. Some of the examples are shown in Fig 2.2.

The use of CT scan as a diagnostic tool was not initially accepted due to the lack of evidence. [34] shows the evolution of the statements from different influential medical groups and organizations of different countries. Instead of fully rejecting or generalizing the diagnostic capability of CT images, medical authorities have defined the appropriate use of CT scans which are also supported by scientific studies [42-48]. Some organizations do not recommend medical imaging when extraction methods are abundant and the patient has a mild condition. Other organizations recommend its usage as a primary and/or initial diagnostic tool when extraction methods are not available or scarce, reported inconclusive results, or the patient has moderate to severe condition. Several organizations do rely on the combination of RT-PCR and CT image for confirmation.

Figure 2.2: Example COVID-19 features described in CT images. Adapted from [36]

2.1.2 Comparison to RT-PCR

RT-PCR serves as the main reference of most studies to measure the sensitivity and specificity of CT images for detecting COVID-19. Results show that using chest CT yielded a higher sensitivity performance than RT-PCR [37,48-53] but with low specificity. A new study in Italy [53], however, showed a higher specificity than the other reports as they took account of clinical and epidemiological features. [52] argues that given the contagious nature of COVID-19, sensitivity must be first considered.

When it comes to the settings and turn around time, chest CT is faster than RT-PCR but it will require more stringent measures for the setup since there are more contact points conducting chest CT rather than RT-PCR [50]. However, chest CT exposes the patients to radiation whereas RT-PCR does not.

These evidences put RT-PCR and chest CT in their respective places when detecting COVID-19. It is recommended that if Chest cT is available, it should be used as an initial diagnosis in epidemic areas especially if the condition is moderate to severe rather than RT-PCR given its speed and sensitivity [48-40,50]. It should also serve as a confirmatory tool given the false negative rate of RT-PCR such that even if the RT-PCR findings are negative and CT findings are positive, the patient should still be isolated [54]. Given the abundance of both resources, both tools are recommended to be used [56].

2.1.3 Comparison to Chest X-ray and Lung Ultrasound

With regards to imaging performance, chest CT is recognized as the gold standard imaging for COVID-19 [55]. Lung ultrasound measures up to the higher sensitivity [57] while chest x-ray both has lower sensitivity and specificity [55]. [58] further elaborated that it is difficult to recognize chest x-ray features for COVID-19 within 4-5 days at the onset of the symptoms.

In terms of guidelines, when possible, chest CT is the recommended imaging procedure. However, for people staying in bed, in the intensive care units (ICUs), and emergencies, lung ultrasound and chest x-ray are recommended [56,58] since these equipment are more portable.

There are also other factors in which we can compare the three. With radiation exposure, chest x-ray and chest CT expose the patients to radiation while lung ultrasound lends itself as a radiation-free method [56]. In terms of cost, the following order from most expensive to most affordable is observed: chest CT, chest x-ray, lung ultrasound [59-60]. Chest CT has the largest contact points; thus, a need to stringent cleaning and disinfections while lung ultrasound and chest x-ray provide lesser contact points.

2.2 Reviews and Appraisals

2.2.1 Methodologies

Different reviews of studies considering the use of artificial intelligence for COVID-19 have varying methodologies. Some used guidelines and the others were guided by their own research questions.

Studies considered for the reviews were usually selected using publications whether peer-reviewed (e.g. PubMed, IEEE, Science Direct, Embase) or preprints (e.g. medRxiv, bioRxiv, arXiv), or by using specific search strings. Others were constrained with date ranges while others followed an unstructured study retrieval since the start of the pandemic. Other reviews included the details of their inclusion criteria while others did not.

With regards to reviews with guidelines, for reporting, they used Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) [16] or its other variants (e.g. PRISMA-DTA) [22] and Transparent Reporting of a multivariable prediction model for Individual Prognosis Or Diagnosis (TRIPOD) [17].

PRISMA has a 27 item checklist with 7 major parts:

- | | | | |
|-------------|-----------------|---------------|----------------------|
| 1. Title | 3. Introduction | 5. Results | 7. Other information |
| 2. Abstract | 4. Methods | 6. Discussion | |

Some parts under 'methods' require specifying the search and selection process, data extraction processes, risk bias assessments, synthesis methods, and certainty assessment while results of bias assessments, syntheses, and certainty assessments are some of the items under the 'results' part. The use of its flow chart showing the steps of selecting the studies for reporting is also encouraged. It

should be noted that this is designed as a general checklist that can be used for any studies.

TRIPOD, on the other hand, is specific for prediction model studies and contains 22 items in the checklist with 6 parts:

- | | | |
|-----------------------|------------|----------------------|
| 1. Title and abstract | 3. Methods | 5. Discussion |
| 2. Introduction | 4. Results | 6. Other information |

These are the items under ‘methods’ that are required to be filled out: ‘Source of data’, ‘Participants’, ‘Outcome’, ‘Predictors’, ‘Sample size’, ‘Missing data’, ‘Statistical analysis methods’, ‘Risk Groups’, and ‘Development vs. validation’. ‘Participants’, ‘Model development’, ‘Model specification’, ‘Model performance’, ‘Model updating’ are under Results and ‘Limitations’, ‘Interpretation’, and ‘Implementation’ for Discussion. It was noted that it should be used only for reporting the research and does not measure nor validate the prediction models.

Other guidelines were also observed such as: Critical Appraisal and Data Extraction for Systematic Reviews of Prediction Modeling Studies (CHARMS) [18] to guide them which data to extract from papers, Prediction model Risk Of Bias ASsessment Tool (PROBAST) [19] to assess the risk of bias and CheckList for Artificial Intelligence in Medical imaging(CLAIM) [20] to assess deep learning papers. CHARMS consists of 11 major parts with 34 checklist items. On the other hand, PROBAST contains four major parts with 20 questions with a conclusion that tells whether a prediction model has a low, high, or unclear bias. Lastly, CLAIM contains 7 major parts with a total of 42 items that needed to be filled out in which some of the parts are data processing steps, ground truth details, the models and how they were trained, explainability and model performance.

Figure 2.3: Performance overview of 23 different studies using deep learning to detect COVID-19 from CT images. While this attempts to provide a holistic view of the varying performance of existing systems, it is susceptible to misinterpretation due to being evaluated on different test sets. Adapted from [61]

While most reviews focused on both datasets and models, some focused only on reviewing the datasets, others looked at organizing multiple studies in a generalized pipeline (i.e. listing out various techniques and studies for each step in the workflow to gain a holistic view of the study designs and decisions) [15], and others attempted to give a general view of the performance of different works [61] as seen above. The latter is susceptible to misinterpretation given that the results are not directly comparable to each other as they were measured using different test sets.

2.2.2 Conclusions: Strengths and Weaknesses of Existing Studies, and Recommendations for Further Improvements

Even though these reviews use different methodologies, there is a consensus in their conclusion such as Wynants et al. [14] has summarized—“none of these models is recommended to be used in clinical practice”. There are several existing reviews but we look at three of them in detail given that together they already provide the overall view of where the current systems are good at and why they fail.

Wynants et al. 's review [14] spanned upto July 1, 2020 for studies found in PubMed and Embase through Ovid and upto May 5, 2020 for preprints such as arXiv, medRxiv, bioRxiv. In total they initially identified 37,412 publications with 169 studies to be included in the review consisting of 232 models where 75 of them are imaging studies. They did not include in the report the criteria for the study inclusion and exclusion. These 169 studies covered traditional machine learning to deep learning and applications such as diagnosis, prognosis, and severity of the disease. For diagnosis using medical images, most of the studies they considered reported an almost perfect performance. However, they concluded that these systems cannot still be used in clinical practice due to poor reporting or documentation which led to a score of high risk of bias.

Generally, they also pointed out problems they found on most datasets and models, and their recommendations on how to alleviate them. For datasets, the common problems are high or unclear risk of bias which is due to non-representative selection of participants, high risk of overfitting, unclear reporting (e.g. no information about demographics which affects the system’s applicability), and unclear overlapping for open source data. Their recommendation is to provide information on the target setting such that clinicians will be able to identify if the system is applicable to their needs. On the other hand, the common problems with models are the lack of external validation, high or unclear risk of bias given PROBAST (though they noted that it is harder to apply PROBAST for complex machine learning systems), and lack of appropriate documentation which challenges transparency and reproducibility. They recommended for all models to undergo external validation and to be tested on different settings and populations to explore generalizability and robustness. Overall, they encourage validating, comparing, improving and updating of promising models.

Roberts et al. [13] focused specifically on chest CT and chest x-ray images with application on diagnosis and prognosis. With this, they found 2,212 papers spanning from 3 January 2020 to 3 October 2020 from manuscripts uploaded to EMBASE and MEDLINE, along with the preprints from

bioRxiv, medRxiv, and arXiv. At the end, after excluding duplicates, papers with irrelevant title and/or abstract, studies that did not introduce new models, non-English papers, studies not designed for prognosis or diagnosis, etc., only 62 papers were included in their study. With a similar tone, they also concluded—“none of the models identified are of potential clinical use due to methodological flaws and/or underlying biases”.

They also elaborated further details on why some papers failed to be *included* in the review. For quality screening using the CLAIM checklist, they reported three things documentations commonly lack:

1. How the final model was selected
2. The method of preprocessing of the images
3. The details of the training approach

For detailed analysis, they reported six things not satisfied in the *non-mandatory* CLAIM criteria:

1. External validation
2. Test of robustness or sensitivity analysis of the model
3. Report on the demographics of the data partitions
4. Report on statistical tests used to assess significance of results or determine confidence intervals
5. Report confidence intervals for the performance
6. Sufficiently report the limitations, biases, or issues around generalizability

It should be further emphasized that these are *non-mandatory* criteria which is a design decision of this particular review to further narrow down the list of studies to be included in the detailed analysis.

Focusing on studies using CT images and deep learning, they listed 18 studies that tackle the problem as binary classification problem (COVID or NONCOVID) and/or multiclass classification problem (COVID-19, Viral Pneumonia, Lung Disease, or Normal). They also listed out commonly used techniques such as transfer learning with ImageNet pre-trained weights, use of general adversarial network (GANs) as data augmentation method, and different image modes (e.g. 3D or 2D/2D patches). The performance, they noted, ranged from 70% to 100% AUC but with a caution that the models are not directly comparable to each other given the difference in testing sets.

They also pointed out the patterns in the issues mostly focusing on the datasets, some on methodology, and further gave recommendations.

Two common problems of studies when it comes to datasets are not listing the original source of the images and not considering the duplication and quality issues a dataset may have (i.e. most papers dive straight on visualizing the data and optimizing the models). To elaborate on the duplication and

quality issues, they originally listed three points but had also commented with regards to the resolution of the images. With regards to the resolution of images, they argue that non-DICOM formats lead to a loss of quality and create a lack of consistency or comparability when the resolution is not distributed uniformly throughout the dataset. For datasets in DICOM format, they also pointed out the lack of metadata which can help developers to inform design decisions. On the other hand, the three on their original lists are source issues, frankenstein datasets, and implicit biases on the data. For source issues, they mainly pointed out that imbalanced population representation on datasets will cause the model to overperform (i.e. having images taken from children for the negative samples and adults for the positive samples) and that some datasets are implicitly a subset of one another (i.e. the original image sources or subset information were not included in the metadata). They also caution regarding the use of *Frankenstein datasets*. Like Frankenstein, these datasets were formed independently, and were combined to form a one bigger dataset. A main issue on frankenstein datasets is data leakage—given duplications of samples, copies from the training set can appear on the testing set which leads to overly optimistic performance on the test set and is considered as *cheating*. Lastly, for implicit biases on data, they gave an example that publications will have samples that are “more interesting, unusual, or severe cases of COVID-19”.

Instead of commenting to the models themselves, they listed out insights on the problems with regards to methodology. They argue that information on demographics is crucial for any system. They also raised concerns on studies concluding of outperforming RT-PCR tests when the ground truth is based on it rather than comparing with clinicians. They also discussed that most studies did not provide evidence on the benefits acquired from transfer learning and most of the image scaling decisions are decided using the pre-trained models' specifications rather than clinical usage.

For recommendations, it can be sorted out to four targets. On datasets, they caution the use of public repositories due to the previously discussed issues and recommend to evaluate models in pre-COVID era datasets to further test the capability to classify. On evaluation, they recommend conducting external validation, ensuring the absence of data leakage, including interpretability studies, and the reporting of the operating point, sensitivity, and specificity for both validation and test data. On replicability, they suggested that complete setups must be reported if possible, especially the skeletal settings that dictate the model's characteristics, and raised awareness on the updates the original authors may present. On authors, they recommend assessing the reports or papers to be published by the existing guidelines. They also pointed out that the most missed information is the data pre-processing done and some details on the training should also be taken care of.

Liu et al. [15] expressed their feedback to the works they had reviewed by highlighting “Let AI perform better next time” in their title. Their study spanned two years of work from 2020 to 2022 covering 179 models and 15 datasets. Like Wynants et al., they did not include details about the reason for inclusion and exclusion of studies and no further screening were reported. Although

considering the same data type for CT and chest X-ray like Roberts et al., they only focused on classification and segmentation. Unlike the first two reviews above, they did not follow any guidelines but instead organized the studies by listing down the techniques used for each step in their generalized machine learning pipeline consisting of input data, preprocessing, models, and evaluation. They also had a separate description of the datasets in which 5 was used for CT image classification. For evaluation, they noted two most used metrics: accuracy with a reported average of 94.76% and AUC with 90.13% . They also created a histogram as shown below but it should be noted that direct comparison is invalid such that a model with higher accuracy or AUC does not necessarily mean that it is better than the ones with lower values. This is due to the case that these models were evaluated on different test sets.

Figure 2.4: Distribution of performance of different works on classification of COVID-19 in chest CT images in terms of accuracy and AUC. Adapted from [15]

They narrowed down the problems they observed into three conclusions and later, provided corresponding recommendations: biased model performance evaluation, inappropriate implementation details, and low reproducibility, reliability, and explainability. For biased model performance evaluation, they recommended three things which can be summarized into dataset quantity and quality. They argued that in terms of quantity, researchers should establish big enough benchmarks to move the studies forward. Without an overall benchmark, the results would be incomparable and newly proposed methods can be hardly appreciated. They also added that data leakage and overly optimistic performance were observed due to implicit inappropriate data splits and low samples in the test sets. Second, for inappropriate implementation details, they focused on recommending being careful on applying data augmentation techniques whether through affine transformation or GANs as it may be “too aggressive” or lacking theoretical evidence of its application in the context of medical images. They also recommended using closely related datasets when using pre-trained models rather than using ImageNet or consider domain adaptation algorithms. Lastly, they recommended for future works to report complete documentation to enable reproducibility and to not just output heatmaps to show where the model is looking but also to have medical experts to analyze it together as this will provide information on how to improve the system better.

2.3 Limitations of Reviews and Disagreements

The main goal of reviews is to provide a holistic view of what is happening in a specific area after some period of time. However, there are inherent limitations, observed limitations, and disagreements that can be observed between the reviews.

Inherent limitations are mostly found on the use of methodology, especially those following guidelines. [62] pointed out that using guidelines may let authors “feel deprived of their liberty” while it may “encourage some authors to fabricate spurious information in order to comply with the statement”. Other issues they pointed out are the “missing reporting of research” and introduction of “publication bias” since information was extracted given the guidelines. They stated that these may overlook other important areas for a specific field and that “if only articles that adhere to reporting guidelines are published, a distorted picture of the field will be created”.

An umbrella review on COVID-19 detection in medical imaging [12] provides the observed limitations. In their review, nine databases were searched spanning from inception until 1 September 2020 retrieving 725 records and putting 22 reviews of 165 studies for the final round. They concluded the credibility of these reviews was *critically low*. They provided two significant insights given the reviews: they concluded that the reviews were broad and there is a varying level of agreement between reviews with others showing multiple disagreements.

Other observed disagreements can be found in the primary studies themselves. [35] used CT images from 760 medRxiv and bioRxiv preprints as training data which raises concerns on the usability of the dataset. The two concerns revolved from the loss of quality of the images and the varying number of slices being selected which are believed to have a great impact on the accuracy of the diagnosis. The researchers addressed these feedbacks by asking a senior radiologist from Tongji Hospital, Wuhan, China to validate the dataset and the performance of the model and came to two conclusions:

- (1) “Issues raised does not significantly affect the accuracy of diagnosis decision-making” since “experienced radiologists are able to make accurate diagnosis from low quality CT images”.
- (2) “While it is preferable to read a sequence of CT slices, oftentimes a single-slice of CT contains enough clinical information for accurate decision making.”

In addition, they compared a system trained from data extracted from publications and a system trained on original CT to test on original CTs. They found the former outperforming the ones trained in original CT. Another study on chest x-rays [64-65] has also observed generalizability of their system by testing it on data from different countries despite the “variation in the respiratory effort, image contrast, technique, and resolution between the datasets”. They remarked that this is contrary to what is normally perceived in the field and shed light on the feasibility of this generally occurring. To add, we can explore that even though complete documentation is preferable, it may be possible that only few metadata are significant in handling systems that automatically detect COVID-19.

2.4 Comparative Analysis and Generalizability Studies

When it comes to quantitative comparison, two types of studies exist such as comparative analysis and generalisability.

Usually for studies that did comparative analysis such as [66-68], their methodology consists of selecting one dataset or forming one large dataset and choosing different architectures to train on it. These were pre-trained usually on ImageNet. At the end, they tested the trained models against a test set. The conclusion reached after this type of study consists of selecting which model architecture trained the best.

For studies that deal with generalizability, their methodology commonly consists of selecting multiple datasets (usually less than five independent datasets) and choosing one architecture to train and test on those datasets. In other studies, they select a reference dataset, train different architectures on it and test it on other datasets [69]. A good example of the former is Nguyen et al. [70] of which the confusion matrices are shown below. They used a total of four independent datasets with three being publicly available—China Consortium of Chest CT Image Investigation (CC-CCII) Dataset (China), COVID-CTset (Iran), MosMedDat (Russia)--and UT Southwestern (UTSW) dataset the last being an internal dataset they acquired. Their methodology consists of having two types of training: single dataset training and multiple dataset training. Conclusions derived from these types of study includes pointing out which combination of datasets received the best performance on the corresponding test sets.

(a) Single dataset training

(b) Multiple dataset training

Figure 2.5: Single and multiple dataset training setup. The authors provided an overview of the results as seen in the columns by using the individual datasets and aggregating the results by combining or averaging. Adapted from [70]

2.5 Summary

Overall, this section first covered the nature of the data, the use of chest CT images in detecting COVID-19 in the clinical context, and where it stands in contrast with other approaches such as RT-PCR, CXR, and lung ultrasound. Second, we covered the reviews and appraisals which provided the strengths and weaknesses of existing studies along with their recommendations for further improvements using qualitative methodologies. However, these are prone to observed and inherent limitations, and disagreements. Lastly, other attempts using quantitative approaches such as through comparative analysis and generalization studies have reached the objective of being able to compare to some degree but commonly limited only to the models they trained themselves and some datasets. Thus, we aim to provide a comparative evaluation which will be also be done in a quantitative approach but aims to connect and compare the performance of a number of existing studies and provide conclusions with empirical basis that will leverage on the nature of the data and that also can be compared on the conclusions derived from the reviews.

3 MATERIALS AND METHODS

This chapter is divided into five sections: dataset and model collection, single vs. multiple slice classification, single slice classification, multiple slice classification, and evaluation methodology. The first part reasons regarding the collection of the datasets and models that are considered in this study. We then organized these works into two subtasks using the types of image slices, namely, single and multiple slices. In both categories, we dive deeper to the datasets and models under them—covering their characteristics, conflicts, and challenges in reproducibility. These third and fourth sections present the bulk of this chapter since it will provide perspectives on the validity of the conclusions that can be made. Lastly, we provide an overview of the evaluation methodology used for the results and discussions in the next chapter.

3.1 Data and Model Collection

Chest CT images can be utilized in either 3D or 2D views. We collected datasets and models that utilize 2D views since the majority of the existing works focused on this and it is the view used by medical practitioners when examining if the patient is infected or not [79].

3.1.1 Data Collection

Figure 3.1: Data collection scheme. The dataset constraints are only limited to the following keywords: accessible, complete, chest CT images, and for classification tasks. We also softened the constraints in terms of data issues and released metadata to cover most publicly released datasets and since these are mostly the subject of the negative feedback of the previous reviews (*see Chapter 2*).

Fig 3.1 shows the data collection scheme we followed. We aimed to collect *accessible* and *complete* datasets released since the pandemic covering chest CT images and classification tasks. We prioritized those originally designed for binary classification but we also converted some highly used multi classification datasets to extend the coverage. After collecting, we categorized them depending on how most classification systems used the datasets, i.e. by the type of image slices. This is further discussed in *Section 3.2*.

Since our objective is to evaluate, considering information about splits is important since it is the key in enabling comparisons between studies. We observed that when the original dataset authors released their official splits and models, commonly, other studies that use their datasets follow the same split procedure so they can compare their results to the released models. It is rare to find studies that do not follow the original data split procedure but sometimes they do exist and make their results incomparable to the previous work results. However, if the authors of the dataset did not release the splits, most studies provide their own splits and increase the chance of their results being incomparable to other works. Thus, we prioritized the officially released splits by the dataset authors to enable wider comparisons. If they did not provide the official splits, we looked at the studies that use the datasets and made their splits and models accessible. Finally, if there is no split information available anywhere, we use the whole data for testing.

3.1.2 Model Collection

Figure 3.2: Model collections scheme. The major consideration in collecting the models for evaluation is reproducibility *for testing*.

Fig 3.2 shows our model collection scheme. Our first consideration relies on the dataset authors' release of their own models and if they are usable. If not, we looked at other studies that use their dataset and see if they followed the same split or did their own and if their models are also usable. Finally, if the models are not released but the code to make them and the data split are released and usable, we consider them in our study. To broaden our comparisons, we also considered released models whose datasets are not accessible (e.g. models that won competitions [10]).

The main issue in collecting these models is reproducibility *for testing*. We refer to reproducibility in terms of replicating the system and its behavior, and not strictly the results by the exact numbers. We emphasize reproducibility *for testing* since the reproducibility requirements for replicating the whole system is much higher and testing or evaluation is only one part of it. Given this, we listed the discrepancies from the original reported results in *Appendix A*.

3.2 Single vs. Multiple Slice Classification

As observed, the collected datasets and models can be further categorized between single or multiple slice classification. These two setups are depicted in Fig 3.3, and their comparison is summarized in Table 3.1. Their main difference is the influence of the slices in the decision making process.

Figure 3.3: Single Slice vs. Multiple Slice Classification setups.

Table 3.1: Comparison between Single Slice and Multiple Slice Classification

Single Slice Classification	Multiple Slice Classification
accepts and decides using one image	accepts and decides using multiple images
data can vary depending on the manual slice selection process	data can vary depending on the machine
commonly only have the classification stage	have other stages such as selection of slices, classification stage, or other processes to reach final decision

Earliest works used the single slice classification process. In this setup, only one slice is fed into the system to reach the resulting diagnosis. This makes the selection of this *one* slice highly crucial for patients, medical practitioners, and developers. In the studies considered, the slices were commonly selected by a medical practitioner or an automatic process whose specifications are not always

reported. This setup makes the structure of the classification system simple, i.e. commonly having only the classification stage, but the internal data distribution may vary a lot depending on the criteria of the slice selection and even more when compared with external datasets.

Multiple slice classification, on the other hand, is a subtask which is in the borderline of 2D or 3D view. In this study, we considered it as a 2D view since we view it as slices rather than a 3D CT scan as a whole. The first works in multiple slice classification came out in 2021 with [78] claiming to be the first work to do so, and followed by the release of the ICCV 2021 Competition [10] which encouraged more works using this approach. In this whole setup, the whole image sequence of a patient is labeled with COVID or NONCOVID and is fed into the system. This can be a major challenge since not all slices in the sequence show COVID features [10] which led most systems to consider more stages (e.g. selection of slices, aggregation of decisions on slices). Though this alleviates the great variation in data distribution and reduces the influence of human bias in the system for manually selected slices, the number of slices churned out by the machines may affect the data distribution (i.e. not all machines follow the same slice thickness which affects the total slice number per patient).

3.3 Single Slice Classification

This section provides the collective view of the collected datasets and models covering their characteristics and conflicts specific for single slice classification.

3.3.1 Datasets

Data Characteristics

We collected 8 publicly released datasets in which five of them are originally designed for binary classification and the three of them (COVIDx CT-1, CT-2, and CT-3) were converted from multi class classification (COVID, COMMON PNEUMONIA, and NORMAL) to binary classification.

In Table 3.2, we listed the datasets based on the published date and provided other details such as date coverage, image format, number of citations, split publication, and publication source. These are significant information for evaluation. The published date and date coverage give information that is useful for analyzing data conflicts as we will see in the next part. On the other hand, most of our datasets are saved in lossless format such as PNG and 16-bit TIFF and only one that was saved in a lossy format which is JPEG. The number of citations are included to show the number of works that have used or referred to the dataset. We also included the information if the authors released the official split since they are significant in making the works comparable to each other as discussed in Section 3.1. Lastly, we also include the publication source to indicate whether the work is peer-reviewed or not.

Table 3.2: Datasets for Single Slice Classification.

Dataset	Published Date	Date Coverage	Format	*Citations	Split Published?	Publication Source
1. SARS-COV-2 Ct-Scan [75]	03/15/2020	Not Available	PNG	238	Yes	medrxiv Kaggle
2. iCTCF [76]	04/07/2020	01/25/2020 - 02/20/2020	JPEG	105	No	Nature
3. COVID-CT UC San Diego [64]	06/17/2020	01/19/2020 - 03/25/2020	PNG	616	Yes	arxiv
4. COVIDx CT-1 [77]	12/03/2020	Not Available	PNG	114	Yes	Frontiers in Medicine Kaggle
5. COVIDx CT-2 [78]	02/26/2021	Not Available	PNG	35	Yes	Frontiers in Medicine Kaggle
6. COVID-CTset [79]	04/14/2021	03/05/2020 - 04/23/2020	TIF	120	Yes	Elsevier
7. CO-IRv2 [80]	09/28/2021	Not Available	PNG	16	No	PLOS ONE Journal
8. COVIDx CT-3 [81]	06/02/2022	Not Available	PNG	N/A	Yes	Kaggle

*Number of citations were acquired from Google Scholar (as of August 2022)

With regards to released demographics, existing works commonly released the age and gender information which is shown in Fig 3.4 and 3.5. We distilled it to range and percentage as the common ground since different works have their own way of reporting the metadata considering their *implicit* selected degree of anonymization.

Figure 3.4: Age range per dataset. Reported age is displayed with *orange* as the minimum age and *blue* as the maximum age. SARS-COV-2 Ct-San and CO-IRv2 did not report the age range of their dataset and we signified that as 0 (i.e. without minimum and maximum age). It should be noted that some of them also indicated that some of the samples do not have age information despite reporting the range.

Figure 3.5: Gender percentage per dataset. These are the processed numbers from the existing works since most of them have different ways of reporting the gender information. CO-IRv2 is the only dataset that did not release the gender percentage. COVID-CT UC Sandiego’s breakdown only refers to COVID patients.

Table 3.3 and Fig 3.6 shows the data split breakdown and distribution for each dataset. It should be noted that this is heavily related to the dataset scheme presented in Section 3.1.1 where we discussed the split definition. All datasets released their official splits except iCTCF and CO-IRv2. In this case, we utilized the whole dataset for testing. We also note the following:

- For SARS-COV-2 Ct-Scan, the split definition we followed is from the most voted notebook in Kaggle [82] which only has a train-test split. This is because the dataset authors used multiple versions of dataset splits in their repository as seen in their code and the split included in the python version of their model, which are CSV files, are missing [83]. We observed that most works that used their dataset have followed their own split definition.
- For COVID-CTset, the authors released five splits given they experimented with five folds. However, they did not release the final split nor the final model after their five-fold cross-validation experiment. In this case, we selected their released split for fold 1 since the model for fold 1 yielded the highest results among the other folds.

Table 3.3: Data split breakdown.

Dataset	Train		Validation		Test	
	COVID	NONCOVID	COVID	NONCOVID	COVID	NONCOVID
1. SARS-COV-2 Ct-Scan	978	1 006	-	-	274	223
2. iCTCF	-	-	-	-	4 001	9 979
3. COVID-CT UC San Diego	191	234	60	58	98	105
4. COVIDx CT-1	12 520	49 262	4 529	16 507	4 346	16 845
5. COVIDx CT-2	82 286	61 492	6 244	19 242	6 018	19 640
6. COVID-CTset	1 820	1 916	462	7 860	462	7 860
4. CO-IRv2	-	-	-	-	1 252	1 229
7. COVIDx CT-3	294 552	62 966	8 147	25 578	7 894	25 887

Figure 3.6: Data split distribution percentage. Datasets with no train and valid set information were all used for testing.

Data Conflicts

1. Label Definition

We observed that different studies use different terms when referring to COVID and NONCOVID labels. As shown in Table 3.4, for COVID, they cited the *institutions*, *radiologists*, or *RT-PCR* results as the basis for ground truth. The meaning for NONCOVID is more varied which refers to *Not infected*, *Normal*, *Pneumonia*, or *Other Lung Diseases*.

Label definition and Frankenstein datasets (discussed below in 3. *Frankenstein Datasets*) are also related given the smaller data components making up the bigger dataset can have their own different label definitions.

Table 3.4: Label definition for Single Slice datasets.

Dataset	COVID (confirmed by)	NONCOVID (terms used)
1. SARS-COV-2 Ct-Scan	Hospitals	Not infected
2. iCTCF	RT-PCR	Not infected Other lung diseases present
3. COVID-CT UC San Diego	Senior Radiologist from Tongi Hospital, China	Not infected Other lung diseases present
4. COVIDx CT-1	CNCB	Normal Pneumonia
5. COVIDx CT-2	RT-PCR, Radiologists	Normal Pneumonia
6. COVID-CTset	Negin Radiology Center	Normal
7. CO-IRv2	Hospitals, Radiologists	Not infected Other lung diseases present
8. COVIDx CT-3	RT-PCR, Radiologists	Normal Pneumonia

2. Data Leakage

In our context, data leakage presents itself when images from one patient get distributed to train-valid-test splits which *may* make the evaluation overly optimistic. The only confirmed dataset where data leakage is present is SARS-COV-2 Ct-Scan and CO-IRv2. Other datasets with probable data leakage are iCTCF, and COVID-CT UC San Diego since the former only stated that they were randomly selected from patients while the latter collected their data from publications and the metadata is still a work in progress. COVIDx CT-1, CT-2, and CT-3, and COVID-CTset have controlled their datasets through ensuring that no similar Patient ID exists in other splits. The data leakage information affects only the model that was trained to them and the internal evaluation which led to overly optimistic performance.

3. Frankenstein Datasets

The presence of Frankenstein datasets were raised by [13] (*see Chapter 2*). We recall that like Frankenstein, these datasets were created using other datasets (which can be independent or another Frankenstein dataset). These datasets pose a problem in evaluation since models trained on them are incomparable to each other *unless they follow the same split*. This means that they are not necessarily problematic in evaluation given the latter condition is satisfied. We considered the date coverage of the dataset (Table 3.2), and dataset origins which cover the countries and the original dataset names (Table 3.6), to pinpoint the conflicts as summarized in Fig 3.7.

Figure 3.7: Single Slice Classification: Data conflicts due to frankenstein datasets. This poses a problem in evaluation since models trained in them are incomparable to each other *unless they follow the same split*.

To elaborate this concept, in Fig 3.7a, COVID-CTset is tagged as a *Sure Conflict* with COVIDx CT-2 and CT-3 because it is directly reported as a subset of those two bigger datasets and the original split is not followed in COVIDx CT-2 and CT-3. For example, some of the test samples of COVID-CTset are found in the training samples of COVIDx CT-2 and CT-3 which means models trained in COVIDx-CT2 and CT-3 will, *in normal conditions*, perform very well on the test set of COVID-CTset since they have already been trained in some of those samples. Fig 3.7b shows this relationship along

with the datasets that do not have conflicts with each other.

On the other hand, COVIDx CT-1 does not pose any conflicts even if it contributes to COVIDx CT-2 and CT-3 because the splits are followed. This means, models trained in COVIDX CT-1 can be evaluated with COVIDx CT-2 and CT-3 test sets (and vice versa).

Possible conflicts arise in our datasets with COVID-CT UC San Diego. As [35] discussed, the dataset was created using images found in publications and since the metadata is incomplete, most of the origins of the samples are unknown, making the conflicts to be unknown. We are able to limit the coverage of the conflict assumption to only some datasets because of the reported date coverage as seen in Table 3.2. Datasets with date range or publish date not included in COVID-CT UC San Diego's date range are still comparable.

Table 3.5: Single Slice Classification - Dataset Origins

Datasets	Curated From Past Datasets?	Unknown Countries?	*Mixed	Brazil	China	France	Iran	Russia	USA
1. SARS-COV-2 Ct-Scan				Hospitals of San Paulo	Union Hospital - HUST-UH Liyuan Hospital - HUST-LH				
2. iCTCF									
3. COVID-CT UC San Diego		✓	LUNA 2016 MedPix Radiopaedia						
4. COVIDx CT-1		✓	TCIA Nanjing Drum Tower Hospital LJDC-IDRI Radiopaedia		CNCB/CC-CCII				
5. COVIDx CT-2		✓			Union Hospital - HUST-UH Liyuan Hospital - HUST-LH		Negin Radiology Center Negin Radiology Center	MosMedData	
6. COVID-CTset									
7. CO-IRv2		✓	Radiopaedia SIRM TCIA Nanjing Drum Tower Hospital LJDC-IDRI Radiopaedia	Hospitals of San Paulo					
8. COVIDx CT-3		✓			Union Hospital - HUST-UH Liyuan Hospital - HUST-LH	STOIC	Negin Radiology Center COVID-CT-MD	MosMedData	COVID-19-NY-SBU

* countries were not explicitly stated (refers to "multinational", "some countries")

3.3.2 Models

Models and Reproducibility

We collected 8 trained models as summarized in Table 3.6. This follows the model collection scheme presented in Section 3.1.2. Most of our collected models were released by the dataset creators except DenseNet121 which was trained on SARS-COV-2 Ct-Scan dataset and came from the most voted notebook (*upon collection*) in Kaggle.

Table 3.6: Models and initial reproducibility test for Single Slice Classification

Model	Dataset Used	Initial Reproducibility Test					Remarks
		code	weights	documentation	format (if weights)	framework (if code)	
1. DenseNet121 [82]	SARS-COV-2 Ct-Scan	✓			N/A	Keras, TensorFlow	Most Voted in Kaggle
2. Self-Trans [84]	COVID-CT UC San Diego	✓	✓	✓	.pth	PyTorch	Author's Baseline
3. DenseNet169 [85]	COVID-CT UC San Diego	✓		✓	N/A	PyTorch	Author's Baseline
4. ResNet50V2 + FPN [79]	COVID-CTset	✓	✓	✓	.hdf5	Keras, TensorFlow	Author's Baseline
5. Xception [79]	COVID-CTset	✓	✓	✓	.hdf5	Keras, TensorFlow	Author's Baseline
6. ResNet50V2 [79]	COVID-CTset	✓	✓	✓	.hdf5	Keras, TensorFlow	Author's Baseline
7. COVID-Net CT-1 S [77]	COVIDx CT-1	✓	✓	✓	.ckpt	TensorFlow	Author's Baseline
8. COVID-Net CT-2 S [78]	COVIDx CT-2	✓	✓	✓	.ckpt	TensorFlow	Author's Baseline

The specific details in the model implementation are best viewed using the code and publications released by the authors but we provided an overview below to provide a comparison of the techniques used and novelties introduced if any, and the issues we faced in terms of reproducibility for the objective of testing along with the necessary modifications.

1. DenseNet121 (trained on SARS-COV-2 Ct-Scan dataset)

Figure 3.8: DenseNet121 trained on SARS-COV-2 Ct-Scan dataset. Figure was recreated from the released code in [82]

Training Summary: To fit any input during training, they resize the image to 64x64x3 with inter-area interpolation and normalized by dividing with 255. They also used the following *randomized* data augmentation techniques:

- Rotation range (360)
- Width shift range (0.2)
- Height shift range (0.2)
- Zoom range (0.2)
- Horizontal flip
- Vertical flip

The whole architecture is shown in Fig 3.8. The author did not reason for selecting DenseNet121 nor experiment using other architectures. In general, DenseNets [109] are known for their *dense skip connections* rather than the *sparse skip connections* as originally introduced in ResNets [88]. This inherits all of the advantages ResNets introduced along with the strengthening of feature propagation, feature reuse, and reduction in computational costs due to reducing the number of parameters. These advantages were shown empirically through the image recognition benchmarks.

Other highlighted techniques are listed below:

- Batch size: 64
- Optimizer: Adam
- Loss: Categorical Cross Entropy
- Annealer: Reduce learning rate on plateau (monitoring validation accuracy, on factor of 0.5 with patience where the lower bound for the learning rate is 1-3e)
- Epochs: 50
- Best Model Selection: Early stopping via validation loss

Testing Summary: They used the same image transformations from the training phase but without the data augmentation. The images are normally fed to the model and are assigned with a confidence score. The predicted class is determined using the maximum confidence score.

Comments on Reproducibility for Testing: Using the exact code itself, there have been discrepancies from the original results (*see Appendix A*). This is due to the *local* use of random seeds during training which does not cover the randomness introduced in data augmentation.

2. Self-Trans with DenseNet-169 backbone (trained on COVID-CT UC San Diego dataset)

Figure 3.9: Self-Trans with DenseNet-169 backbone training paradigm. Adapted from [86]

Training Summary: As seen in Fig 3.9, the training phase was split into two parts: the self-supervised learning and the supervised learning stages. The main idea is to use self-supervised learning for weight initialization, then use these weights for supervised learning. The motivation for this two part training process is the issue of the use of vanilla transfer learning, i.e. it involves the use of pre-trained weights on large scale datasets that have different feature and label data than CT images as starting weights.

In the first part of their method, they used an ImageNet pre-trained DenseNet-169 as a starting point and used self-supervised learning to adjust these weights using the LUNA dataset then the COVID-CT data. The process starts with taking two images to act as a query and a key such that for each of the images, they perform a random resize crop to 224 between the scale range of 0.2 and 1.0. After that, they used the following data augmentation techniques:

- Random Apply of Color Jitter (0.4, 0.4, 0.4, 0.1) with probability of 0.8
- Random Grayscale with probability of 0.2
- Random Apply of Gaussian Blur (0.1, 2.0) with probability of 0.5
- Random Horizontal Flip
- Normalization with mean=[0.485, 0.456, 0.406] and std=[0.229, 0.224, 0.225]

Then the forward pass process is that these images are then fed into two encoders which translates the images into a representation q and k for comparison using the contrastive loss L where τ is an annealing parameter :

$$L = -\log \frac{\exp(q \cdot k / \tau)}{\exp(q \cdot k / \tau) + \sum \exp(q \cdot k)} \quad (1)$$

If the query q and key k images are determined to belong to the same image, the pair is labeled as

positive; otherwise, the pair is labeled as negative. Then, the weights are updated as given by the equations below (as adapted from [86]):

$$\theta_q \leftarrow \theta_q - \alpha \frac{\partial L}{\partial \theta_q} \quad (2)$$

$$\theta_k \leftarrow m\theta_k + (1 - m)\theta_q \quad (3)$$

The first equation is for updating the weights of the query encoder θ_q which utilizes backpropagation and a learning rate α while the second equation updates the weight θ_k which does not make use of backpropagation, rather, it makes use of the weighted average of past states through a momentum coefficient ($m=0.999$) and past states. The weights of the encoders are learned using the contrastive loss L and this weight update step.

These are some of the hyperparameters for the first part:

- Batch size: 128
- Optimizer: SGD with momentum (0.9) and weight decay (1e-4)
- Loss: Contrastive Loss L
- Epochs: 50

The second part of their method involves supervised learning. The system resizes the input to 256x256x3 then does a random resize crop to 224x224 with scale range of 0.5 to 1.0. They also used the following data augmentation techniques:

- Random Horizontal Flip
- Color Jitter with brightness (0.2) and contrast (0.2)
- Normalization with mean=[0.45271412, 0.45271412, 0.45271412] and std=[0.33165374, 0.33165374, 0.33165374]

Then, they used the weights from the first part as the starting weights and fine-tuning it using the COVID-CT UC San Diego dataset without freezing the pre-trained weights.

These are some of the hyperparameters for the second part:

- Batch size: 4
- Optimizer: Adam
- Loss: Cross Entropy
- Annealer: Cosine Annealing
- Epochs: 3,000
- Best Model Selection: via max epoch

Testing Summary: The inference phase involves only the supervised learning stage. It starts with directly resizing to 224x224x3 and normalizing it with the same values of mean and standard deviation indicated during training. The image is then fed to the model and gets the confidence score

of the results. The class with the maximum confidence score determines the predicted class label.

Comments on Reproducibility for Testing: The authors released the weights and the code used for prediction. There is a slight difference with our results (*see Appendix A*) but this may be due to rounding and consideration of decimal places (i.e. the authors only used two decimal places which is not in the percentage format) since there are no sources of randomness given that the weights were provided and the image preprocessing procedure did not employ any randomness.

3. DenseNet-169 (trained on COVID-CT UC San Diego dataset)

Training Summary: The system takes any input image sizes and resizes them to 256x256x3 then does a random resized crop to transform to 224x224 with the scale range of 0.5 to 1.0. Then, they do data augmentation such as the following:

- Random Horizontal Flip
- Normalization, mean=[0.485, 0.456, 0.406], std=[0.229, 0.224, 0.225]

For the model, they used an ImageNet pre-trained DenseNet-169 in PyTorch and did fine-tuning without using freezing the pretrained layers given the following hyperparameters:

- Batch Size: 10
- Optimizer: Adam
- Loss: Cross Entropy Loss
- Annealer: Cosine Annealing
- Epoch: 3,000
- Best Model Selection: via max epoch

Testing Summary: The inference phase started with resizing the input image to 224x224x3, doing a center crop, and finally, applying the normalization computed from the training examples. The image is then fed to the model and gets the confidence score of the results. The class with the maximum probability determines the predicted class label.

Comments on Reproducibility for Testing: The authors did not release the weights of the model but released the code. Despite this, there are reported discrepancies (*see Appendix A*). This is due to the absence of controlled sources of randomness which is caused specifically by the data augmentation process.

4. ResNet50V2 + FPN (trained on COVID-CTset dataset)

Training Summary: The system accepts inputs with the shape of 512x512x1. Their data is specifically a 16-bit TIFF which was introduced as a novelty in their work. They did not introduce any resizing or cropping since their data conforms to the required inputs.

For randomized data augmentation, they used the following:

- Horizontal Flip
- Zoom range (0.05)
- Width shift range (0.05)
- Shear range (0.05)
- Vertical Flip
- Rotation range (0 to 360)
- Height shift range (0.05)

Figure 3.10: ResNet50V2 with FPN architecture. Adapted from [79]

With regards to the architecture, as seen in Fig 3.10, the authors used a Feature Pyramid Network (FPN) [87] with a ResNet50V2 backbone [88]. They used FPN to take advantage of extracting features on different scales. They argued that this is beneficial since even though they used a uniform image size as an input to preserve the image, COVID-19 infections occur in different scales. On the other hand, an ImageNet pretrained ResNet50V2 as a backbone was used given its capability to reduce data corruptions given the residual units. In addition, in [88] it was stated that ResNetV2 takes advantage of pre-activation rather than the conventional post-activation which helps in reducing overfitting for deeper networks compared to ResNetV1 [110]. Then, they took this architecture and further did fine-tuning without freezing the pre-trained layers given some of the following hyperparameters:

- Batch Size: 10
- Optimizer: Nadam
- Loss: Categorical Cross Entropy
- Epoch: 50
- Best Model Selection: Early stopping via max validation accuracy

Since the authors stopped at the results of the 5-fold validation and did not finalize their model, we picked their fold 1 trained model given the reported results were consistently higher than the other folds.

Testing Summary: For the inference phase, the system accepts input of the shape 512x512x1 with no other image preprocessing. The image is then fed to the model and gets the confidence score of the results. The class with the maximum probability determines the predicted class label.

Comments on Reproducibility for Testing: We were able to get the exact results as reported in their paper(see Appendix A). This is attributed to the release of the weights, use of four decimal places, and with no other image preprocessing included to the testing stage.

To test it with the other datasets, we found that the original setup does not accommodate any inputs of different size, i.e. in terms of width, height, and channel, for inputs with three channels. Due to this, we used OpenCV's BGR2Gray to convert to one channel and resize inputs to 512x512x1 using Keras' resizing function then crop to true aspect ratio if the width and height varies.

5. Xception (trained on COVID-CTset dataset)

The setup is similar to 4. *ResNet50V2 + FPN* above with the only difference that the fine-tuned Xception model was used.

In the original paper [89], Xception or *Extreme Inception*, as its name suggests, is inspired by the original *Inception* [112] architecture where the difference is the replacement of the inception modules by depthwise separable convolutions. Depthwise separable convolutions are different such that instead of applying the point-wise convolution operation then performing different convolutional or pooling operations on *all* of the channels and concatenating them later, the convolutional operations are applied per channel and later on, passed to a point-wise convolutional operation. Empirical results on image recognition benchmarks shows it outperforms InceptionV3 [111].

6. ResNet50V2 (trained on COVID-CTset dataset)

The setup is similar to 4. *ResNet50V2 + FPN* above with the only difference that the pretrained and fine-tuned ResNet50V2 without the FPN stage was used.

7. COVID-NET CT-1 S (trained on COVIDx CT-1)

Training Summary: The system accepts 512x512x3 and no further image transformations were seen implemented. They also employed the following randomized data augmentation techniques:

- Cropping box jitter (0.025)
- Horizontal and Vertical Shear (0.15)
- Intensity Shift (10)
- Rotation (10)
- Horizontal Flip
- Scaling (0.2)

Figure 3.11: COVID-Net S architecture. Adapted from [78]

Instead of designing the network manually, the authors used a “machine-driven design exploration” to automatically come up with the architecture as seen in Fig 3.11 to tailor the network for COVID-19 CT purposes. They did not give details about their “machine-driven design exploration” procedure.

Their resulting architecture has four features. The first two is the use of pointwise convolutions for both lowering and expanding the channel dimensions. Aside from this, they also used a replicator to increase channel dimensions. Lastly, they also employed depthwise convolution with stride for PRPE-S and without stride for PRPE. PRPRE means “projection-replication-projection-expansion” pattern. They also emphasized the presence of connections between layers like DenseNets but used a long range and selective version. They released both the L [77] and S [78] versions of the architecture but we chose the S version given its inference time and the performance gap, i.e. COVID-NET CT-1 S has 93.2% Accuracy and is faster while COVID-NET CT-1 L has 94.5%. They also used the following hyperparameters:

- Batch Size: 8, with rebalancing the distribution of classes
- Optimizer: SGD with momentum 0.9
- Loss: Cross Entropy with L2 regularization
- Epoch: 17
- Best Model Selection: Early stopping via validation accuracy

Testing Summary: The system accepts 512x512x3 and images with bigger height and width. Upon loading the image, they convert it to grayscale and do an “auto body crop” which the author had defined. The specific details of this function can be found in their repository [90]. Then, they resize the image to 512x512 using inter-cubic interpolation and normalized it by dividing with 255. Lastly, they restack the images to form the three channels before feeding to the network.

Comments on Reproducibility for Testing: Regarding the preprocessing, it accommodates only images whose height and width are ≥ 512 due to their “auto-crop” procedure. Given this, we

introduced a modification in their code to accommodate images with smaller dimensions. The modification is as follows: after loading the image to grayscale, we resize the images to 512x512 by using Keras' resizing function with crop to true aspect ratio. The next parts are the same with the original code, i.e. normalizing the image by dividing with 255 and restacking the images to form the three channels before feeding to the network. By introducing this part, we noticed some discrepancies from the original results (*see Appendix A*).

We had no issues in reproducing their trained model since the authors were able to release the weights. Overall, one drawback of the work is the use of TensorFlow v1 given the current use of the framework.

8. COVID-Net CT-2 S (trained on COVIDx CT-2)

Similar steps were followed as in 7. *COVID-NET CT-1 S* above. The only difference is the dataset where it was trained. In #7, it was trained in COVIDx CT-1 and here, it was trained on COVIDx CT-2.

Model Conflicts

Model conflicts arise when two models cannot be compared to each other because the datasets used for training them conflict each other. Thus, the chart in Fig. 3.12 relies on the data conflicts presented in Fig 3.7.

Most of the model conflicts that arise from single classification models were trained on SARS-COV-2 Ct-Scan (DenseNet121), COVID-CT UC San Diego (Self-Trans with DenseNet-169 and DenseNet-169), COVID-CTset (ResNet50V2 with FPN, Xception, and ResNet50V2), and COVIDx CT-2 (COVID-Net CT-2 S). This shows that these works are not totally incomparable to each other as claimed by the reviews.

Figure 3.12: Single Slice Classification - model conflict chart

3.3.3 Effects on Evaluation: Summary of Data-Model Conflicts

Finally, based on Fig 3.7 and 3.12, we form the data-model conflict chart (Fig 3.13) for single slice classification.

Figure 3.13: Single Slice Classification - data and model conflict chart.

3.4 Multiple Slice Classification

This section provides the collective view of the collected datasets and models covering their characteristics and conflicts specific to multiple slice classification.

3.4.1 Datasets

Data Characteristics

We collected 7 publicly available datasets with two datasets (MosMed Data and ZAFFINO Dataset) covering only positive samples, three datasets (COVID-CT-MD, MAFTOUNI, and New SARS-COV-2) converted from multi classification (COVID/CAP/NONCOVID; COVID/HEALTHY/OTHERS) to binary classification (COVID/NONCOVID), and the remaining as originally designed for binary classification with DataBiox HRCTv1 originally has further separate labels for image features which are Ground Glass Opacity (GGO), Crazy Paving, and Air Space Consolidation.

In Table 3.7, we summarize the similar set of information we collected in Single Slice Classification. As seen in the date columns, studies in Multiple Slice Classification came later than Single Slice Classification. The image formats are more varied and close to the raw data condition (e.g. DICOM, NRRD, NiFTI) which we converted to PNG using [91] given the patient-level collection but still

anonymized. We also performed data cleaning such as removing other included views (e.g. x-ray scans). In addition, we also included the number of citations from Google Scholar. It should be noted, however, that the New SARS-COV-2 citations were mostly from the Single Slice version. We were not able to find any complete works that use this patient-level dataset. With regards to split publication, most of them did not publish; thus, we use all of the data mostly for testing. Publication source is also included to indicate whether the work is peer-reviewed or not.

Table 3.7: Datasets for Multiple Slice Classification

Dataset	Published Date	Date Coverage	Format	*Citations	Split Published?	Publication Source
1. New SARS-COV-2 [92]	03/15/2020	N/A	PNG	238	No	Kaggle
2. MosMed Data [72]	05/22/2020	03/01/2020 - 03/25/2020	NIFTI	110	No	Digital Diagnostics Journal
3. ZAFFINO Dataset [73]	02/16/2021	N/A	NRRD	11	No	MDPI Bioengineering
4. COVID-CTset [79]	04/14/2021	03/05/2020 - 04/23/2020	TIF	120	Yes	Elsevier
5. COVID-CT-MD [93]	04/29/2021	02/23/2021 - 03/21/2021	DICOM	83	No	Nature
6. MAFTOUNI [94]	06/09/2021	N/A	PNG	17	No	Proceedings of the 2021 IISE Annual Conference
7. DataBiox HRCTv1 [95]	05/06/2022	02/2021 - 09/2021	PNG	0	No	arxiv

*Number of citations are acquired from Google Scholar (as of August 2022)

Figure 3.14: Age range per dataset

Figure 3.15: Gender percentage per dataset

Table 3.8: Data breakdown

Dataset	Patient Count	
	COVID	NONCOVID
1. New SARS-COV-2	80	130
2. MosMed Data	172	-
3. ZAFFINO Dataset	93	-
4. COVIDCt-set	18	237
5. COVID-CT-MD	169	136
6. MAFTOUNI	464	658
7. DataBiox HRCTv1	371	23

Figure 3.16: Slice count per patient

The following datasets are explored in Fig 3.14-3.16 and Table 3.8 in terms of age range, gender percentage, slice count per patient, and data breakdown. With regards to age and gender information, the New SARS-COV-2 dataset is the only dataset that did not release any metadata. In terms of slice information, ZAFFINO Dataset and DataBiox HRCTv1 have the most number of slices per patient, with the latter having an outlier with more than 2,500 image slices for one patient. Since most of the datasets did not release splits (except COVID-CTset which has 77 COVID and 45 NONCOVID patients in the train set), we use all of their data for testing.

Data Conflicts

For multiple slice classification, only label definition and frankenstein dataset issues were found. The issue with data leakage was not found since most of them did not release splits or have based the splits in the patient level.

1. Label Definition

Each study used their own terms to signify what they meant by COVID and NONCOVID as seen in Table 3.9 below. Unlike Single Slice Classification datasets, the label definition for COVID is more varied through the confirmation from the *image features*, *epidemiological information* (i.e. if the patient is in the area with greater number of COVID positive people), *radiologists*, *hospitals* or

centers, clinical data, and RT-PCR. On the other hand, most works used *Healthy*, *Normal*, and *Other Pulmonary Diseases* to refer to NONCOVID labels.

Table 3.9: Label definition for Multiple Slice Datasets

Dataset	COVID	NONCOVID
1. New SARS-COV-2	RT-PCR	Healthy Other Pulmonary Directions
2. MosMed Data	Clinical Data Image Features	N/A
3. ZAFFINO Dataset	Image features Radiologist RT-PCR	N/A
4. COVIDCt-set	Negin Radiology Center	Normal
5. COVID-CT-MD	Clinical Findings Epidemiology Image Features Radiologists RTPCR (some patients)	Normal Other Pulmonary Diseases
6. MAFTOUNI	Clinical Findings Epidemiology Image Features Radiologists RTPCR (some patients)	Normal Other Pulmonary Diseases
7. DataBiox HRCTv1	Image Features Radiologists RTPCR	Negative

2. Frankenstein Datasets

The only Frankenstein dataset is MAFTOUNI as shown in Table 3.10 showing the data origins. This dataset also shows that Frankenstein datasets can occur in levels, i.e. a Frankenstein dataset can have components that are also Frankenstein datasets. This is seen in COVID-19 Segmentation Dataset which are mostly from SIRM and Radiopaedia. Thus, as seen in Fig 3.17, this means that any models trained in the MAFTOUNI dataset are incomparable with those trained in MosMed Data, COVIDCt-set, and COVID-CT-MD (and vice versa).

Table 3.10: Multiple Slice Classification - dataset origins

Dataset	Country	Source
1. New SARS-COV-2	Brazil	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public Hospital of the Government Employees of Sao Paulo Metropolitan Hospital of Lapa
2. MosMed Data	Russia	Municipal Hospitals in Moscow
3. ZAFFINO Dataset	Italy	Azienda Ospedaliera Pugliese-Ciaccio
4. COVIDCt-set	Iran	Negin Radiology Center
5. COVID-CT-MD	Iran	Babak Imaging Center
6. MAFTOUNI	Belgium	COVID-CT Dataset
	China	COVID-CT-MD
	Greece	Cohen
	Iran	MosMedData
	Italy	COVIDCt-set
	Japan	COVID-19 CT Lung and Infection Segmentation Dataset
	Portugal	COVID-19 Segmentation Dataset*
7. DataBiox HRCTv1	Iran	Milad hospital emergency rooms

**Originally from SIRM and Radiopaedia*

Figure 3.17: Multiple Slice Classification - data conflict chart

3.4.2 Models

Models and Reproducibility

We were able to collect five models as summarized in Table 3.11. We only replicated the Top 3 and the Top 5 model from the MIA COV19D ICCV 2021 Competition [10] since other models depend on other code repositories which require a certain input (e.g. 3D inputs), weights were not released, the code released are unusable or the documentation are insufficient for the replication of the work for testing.

The first two models' dataset, MIA COV19D, was a competition dataset from ICCV 2021. They also released the second competition with the second version of the dataset for ECCV 2022 [11]. MIA COV19D was not acquired in this study but is available upon signing the EULA given by the organizers.

Table 3.11: Models and initial reproducibility test for Multiple Slice Classification

Model	Dataset Used	Initial Reproducibility Test					Remarks
		code	weights	documentation	format (if weights)	framework (if code)	
1. Deep Wilcoxon [96]	*MIA COV19D	✓	✓	✓	.pt	PyTorch	ICCV'21 Top 3
2. TAC - ResNet14 [97]	*MIA COV19D COVID-CTset	✓	✓	✓	.ag	Keras, TensorFlow	ICCV'21 Top 5
3. ResNet50V2 + FPN [79]	COVID-CTset	✓	✓	✓	.hdf5	Keras, TensorFlow	Author's Baseline
4. Xception [79]	COVID-CTset	✓	✓	✓	.hdf5	Keras, TensorFlow	Author's Baseline
5. ResNet50V2 [79]	COVID-CTset	✓	✓	✓	.hdf5	Keras, TensorFlow	Author's Baseline

*Dataset not acquired

The specific details in the model implementation are best viewed using the code and publications released by the authors but we provide an overview below for the readers to provide a comparison on the techniques used and novelties introduced if any, and the issues we faced in terms of reproducibility along with the necessary modifications.

1. Deep Wilcoxon (trained on MIA COV19D)

Figure 3.18: Deep Wilcoxon Methodology. Adapted from [96]

Training Summary: The system accepts a sequence of input images of any size from a patient. The slices were then selected by getting the 30%~60% sample sizes in the center of CT scan as seen in Fig 3.18. This was determined empirically by their experiments on the competition dataset. It is suggested in their paper that they used data augmentation and normalization. However, looking at their released code repository, there were no data augmentation and normalization that were performed.

In the same code repository, they first established the definition of positive and negative distribution. For positive distribution, it has a mean=1 and a std=0.2 and for negative distribution, they assigned a mean=-1 and a std=0.2. They load simultaneously a positive and a negative image and both get fed to the model (the swin-transformer block then fully connected layer). The authors did not reason about the selection of the model. The loss is then computed by the summation of the two individual losses, one from the positive and the other from the negative, each computed by Mean Squared Error.

The model gets evaluated with the validation set every 5 epochs. The validation part consists of two stages and the computation of the validation metrics. The two stages consist of one for the positive images and one for the negative images. In both of the stages, the image is fed to the model and passed to the wilcoxon rank test. The wilcoxon rank test that was used was defined in SciPy [98]. If the result is a p value that is less than 0.01, the prediction was assigned as COVID; otherwise, NONCOVID.

For a quick list of some of the hyperparameters, they used the following:

- Batch size:10
- Optimizer: AdamW (Adam with weight decay)
- Loss: Mean Squared Error
- Epoch: 100
- Best Model Selection: There is no information on [96] how the released model was determined. In their code repository, the parts that save the model were commented out. One part is when the model got a validation F1-Score greater than 0.9. The second one is that the model is saved every epoch.

Testing Summary: The system accepts a sequence of input images of any size from a patient. The slices were then selected by getting the 30%~60% sample sizes in the center of CT scan just as done in the training process. Then, the selected images undergo image transformation as the following:

- Resizing to 224x224x3
- Normalized using mean = 0.39221061670618984 and std = 0.11469786773730418

After the transformation, those images are fed to the model. The output from each of the images in that sequence is fed to the wilcoxon rank test and gets the output p value. If the p value is less than 0.05, the person is identified to have COVID; otherwise, NONCOVID.

Comments on Reproducibility for Testing: The authors have released the model and no modifications are needed. However, we cannot test the replicated system's results for discrepancies since the dataset where it was trained was not acquired. Though upon checking, there is no randomness present that can change the results from the original.

2. TAC - ResNet14 (trained on MIA COVID19D and COVID-CTset)

Training Summary: The system accepts a sequence of images from a patient of any size and resizes them to 224x224x3 using the default interpolation in OpenCV which is inter-linear. No other image transformation nor data augmentation was performed. There are also no selection algorithms introduced.

For the model, they trained different architectures on the whole set of images from the patients but we selected their ResNet14 since it has the highest performance results among other models. It was trained using AutoML via AutoGluon. The resulting best config was not released by the authors; thus, not much information regarding the hyperparameters were known. The following hyperparameters were listed in their paper [97]:

- Batch size: 16
- Epoch: 15
- Best Model Selection: As suggested in the paper, either the training reaches the set epoch or stops when the training goes over 4 hours.

They only introduced the post processing phase in internal testing such that they identified the person to have COVID or none via the label counts on the slices, i.e. if the maximum number of slices were labeled with COVID, then the person is identified with it; otherwise, the person is not infected. This decision was based on their empirical experiments with different thresholds and found that the best results were obtained if the slices have 30% COVID labels or more.

Testing Summary: The system accepts a sequence of images from a patient of any size and resizes it to 224x224x3. These are directly passed to the trained model and the result for each image slice is collected. Similar to the internal testing during training, the patient is diagnosed with COVID if the maximum number of the label results are COVID; otherwise, the patient is not infected.

Comments on Reproducibility for Testing: The authors were able to release the model and no modifications were introduced to be able to test it with other settings. We were not able to counter check the performance results against the dataset they used; however, there are no suggestions in their process that will keep us from getting the same results.

3. ResNet50V2 + FPN (trained on COVID-CTset dataset)

The model is exactly the same as the single classification version. The only difference is the authors introduced a selection algorithm and a post-processing phase. Given this, we only discuss the selection algorithm and the post-processing phase.

Training Summary: The motivation of the selection algorithm is to only select images that are in the “Open-lung” mode and not in the “Closed-lung” mode as seen in Fig 3.19 since the former mode

shows the COVID-19 features. The selection algorithm is elaborated in Fig 3.20 and can be understood as having two phases: selecting the threshold value per each image given the number of dark pixels (pixel value less than 300) and selecting the images in the slices satisfying the condition based on the threshold value. The first part is as follows. For each image in a sequence of CT scans from one patient, the image is cropped by the Analysis Region (defined by preset values of the four corners) then dark pixels are counted. The threshold was set by subtracting the maximum and minimum dark pixels and dividing by 1.5. They did not specify the reason regarding the 1.5 value. The second part then uses the threshold such that for each image in the sequence, the dark pixels are counted and if the dark pixel count value is greater than the threshold, the image is selected; otherwise, the image is discarded. The selected images from a patient are then fed to the model.

After all selected images from a patient was fed to the model and each image has a label of COVID or NONCOVID, they place the following post-processing stage which relies on the condition that if at least 10% of the selected slices are labeled with COVID, then the patient is declared to have the disease. Otherwise, the patient is not infected. No rationale was given on the use of the threshold.

Figure 3.19: Open-lung and Closed-lung node mode. Adapted from [79]

Figure 3.20: CT scan selection algorithm of ResNet50V2 with FPN. Adapted from [79]

Testing Summary: The inference phase uses the same testing scheme as the single classification version with the addition of the selection algorithm and post-processing phase as used in the training phase.

Comments on Reproducibility for Testing: We were also able to get the exact reported figures as given by the authors when we used the system in their own dataset. In addition to the comments written in the single slice classification version, the determined value of a dark pixel (pixel less than 300) in the selection algorithm is not flexible to match those images that are in the 8-bit format since it is determined by the 16-bit images. We have to adjust it to 100 to accommodate the 8-bit images. We have pinned down this number upon looking at the resulting images after selection just as what the authors did. However, this is still a drawback since having one value to define the value of a dark pixel would hinder its adaptability for images from other environments.

4. Xception (trained on COVID-CTset dataset)

The setup is similar to 3. *ResNet50V2 + FPN* above with the only difference that the fine-tuned Xception model was used.

5. ResNet50V2 (trained on COVID-CTset dataset)

The setup is similar to 3. *ResNet50V2 + FPN* above with the only difference that the fine-tuned ResNet50V2 model was used.

Model Conflicts

All models are comparable with each other except the TAC ResNet14 against the models trained in COVID-CTset data because a portion of the dataset, which was not identified by the authors, was used in training the model.

3.4.3 Effects on Evaluation: Summary of Data-Model Conflicts

There are only two data-model conflicts: one is with the COVID-CTset models with the MAFTOUNI dataset given that COVID-CTset is part of the MAFTOUNI dataset as seen in Table 3.10 and second, the TAC ResNet14 with the COVID-CTset as discussed in Model Conflicts above. However, for the first conflict, it should be noted that the image format used in MAFTOUNI is PNG while COVID-CTset uses the TIF image format.

Figure 3.21: Multiple Slice Classification - data and model conflict chart.

3.5 Evaluation Methodology

3.5.1 The Leaderboard Approach

The center of the leaderboard approach is the evaluation metrics. The use of evaluation metrics allows us to distill broad information into focused measures. Each metric has its own strengths and weaknesses but definitely, when used with other assessments, it helps piece the picture of evaluation.

We used four metrics: Accuracy, AUC, F1-Score, and Precision. This metric set is commonly used in most existing studies in our context. For F1-Score and Precision, we used the weighted version since

we want to look at the result with prevalence involved. With this, we removed Recall from our list since the weighted version of Recall is equivalent to Accuracy.

In our experiment setups, we mainly ask the following:

- Given a metric, how do the models rank against each other?
- Looking at cross-dataset generalization, how are the models able to cope with other datasets?
- Under the lens of known conflicts, does the overly optimistic performance assumption hold?
- How does the model fare on valid and invalid data-model matchups?

3.5.2 Beyond Leaderboard

If the evaluation metrics show the summarized view, in this section, we look at the pieces and other views of the behavior of the systems through the following:

TP, FN, TN, and FP on Deconstructed Confusion Matrix and Predicted Probability Distribution. For both single and multiple slice classification, we looked at the confusion matrix in a modified way to accommodate all the data and model matchups, and in a fine-grained manner by looking at the probability distributions. This will show further details on the results of the evaluation metrics above since it will tell if the model is confidently right or wrong in both or either of the classes. A model that is confidently wrong even if it scores high in the metrics can be dangerous to use.

Model Calibration. Since single slice classification models were all able to give predicted probabilities in which the multiple slice classification models did not, we also looked into model calibration. Understanding model calibration is significantly important for high-stake applications such as medical diagnosis [99-101]. With model calibration, we want to know if the probability assignments reflect the fraction of positives. In other words, in 100 samples that the models predicted with 90% probability of having COVID-19, we expect that 90% should be correctly classified. Recent studies put forward that despite the high performance of modern neural networks, most of them are not well calibrated [100-101].

We give two views of model calibration by using reliability diagrams to get a grasp of the whole view, and Expected Calibration Error (ECE) to distill it into one value which we coupled with classification error to view the correlation between the measures. We adapted the corresponding definitions from [100].

Reliability diagrams show the relationship of the mean predicted value against the fraction of the positives. Since we have finitely many samples, it uses the concept of binning which is its important hyperparameter [101], i.e. it drives the visual representation such that smaller bins will result in smoother curves and larger bins to ragged curves. In addition, smaller bins are usually used for smaller datasets and larger bins for larger datasets given this ragged curve behavior. For interpretation,

a perfectly calibrated model has the identity function such that the mean predicted value perfectly corresponds with a fraction of the positives. By definition, any curve away from this is said to be miscalibrated. The fraction of positives or simply the accuracy is computed as:

$$acc(B_m) = \frac{1}{|B_m|} \sum_{i \in B_m} 1(\widehat{y}_i = y_i) \quad (4)$$

This is simply read as the accuracy given a bin on a part of interval M (B_m) is equivalent to the average of the instances where the predicted class \widehat{y}_i equals the actual class y_i . On the other hand, the mean predicted value per bin is computed by averaging the probabilities given the bin as mathematically summarized below:

$$conf(B_m) = \frac{1}{|B_m|} \sum_{i \in B_m} \widehat{p}_i \quad (5)$$

[100] gave an important note in interpreting reliability diagrams:

Note that reliability diagrams do not display the proportion of samples in a given bin, and thus, cannot be used to estimate how many samples are calibrated.

ECE sums all the information in the reliability diagram by getting the difference between the accuracy and the confidence given a bin and then averaging in all n samples. The equation is as follows:

$$ECE = \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{|B_m|}{n} \left| acc(B_m) - conf(B_m) \right| \quad (6)$$

Saliency Maps. We also look at Grad-CAM [102] in understanding “where the model looks” given the prediction. In this work, instead of applying it to one sample and showing the differences between the models’ outputs, we implemented a stacked approach via averaging which gives the global view of the model’s behavior as seen in the example in Fig. 4.22. This is helpful since it will help us understand where the model usually looks for COVID-19 predictions and if they make sense on average. This works since we are expecting mostly the same CT scan view arrangement. The only disadvantage of this approach is that slight variations in image positioning (e.g. rotations, shifts, zooms) should be kept in mind in interpreting the results. We used the averaged result since using the max to show all lighted areas with a large dataset would not give us any useful information since at worst case, all parts may mostly light up.

For models developed in Tensorflow/Keras version 2, we used the official Grad-CAM from [103]. For COVID-Net CT-1 S and CT-2 S which used Tensorflow v1, we used the author’s implementation as in [81]. For PyTorch model implementations, we used the python package *torch-cam* [104].

We only applied it to single slice classification focusing on the true positives since getting a global view on multiple slices with many slices following different slice thickness would be confusing. However, if a uniform slice thickness is followed, a global 3D view can be constructed to show the global behavior of the model and would be useful to tell which slices or part of the lungs is the most informative or defining factor for detected COVID-19 features.

Figure 3.22: Averaged Grad-CAM. The heat maps corresponding to each sample prediction are normally acquired and then averaged to get the global view of the behavior of the model. It should be kept in mind, however, that slight variations in image positioning (e.g. rotations, shifts, zooms) may be present in the samples.

To supplement, we also show the following: a breakdown of each model’s total number of parameters and FLOPS in *Appendix B* for computational costs; UMAP of each dataset for single slice classification in *Appendix C*; and the full Grad-CAM results covering true positives, false negatives, true negatives, and false positives in *Appendix D*. The UMAP section was broken down to show COVID vs NONCOVID per each dataset, the COVID class covering all datasets, as well as the NONCOVID class on all datasets to see if the features suggest clustering or separability.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section has three main parts—the first two covers the results for both single slice classification and multiple slice classification, and the last covers the general discussions. For the first two parts, we cover the leaderboard approach which uses the evaluation metrics—Accuracy, AUC, weighted F1-Score, and weighted Precision—to see where each model stand against the others given with or without the lens of the conflicts; and beyond the leaderboard which covers the deconstructed confusion matrix, predicted probability distribution, model calibration, and saliency maps. Other supplemental results can be found in the Appendix such as the discrepancies from the original results, total parameters and FLOPS, UMAP visualizations, and the complete averaged Grad-CAM outcomes. In the general discussions, we discuss the takeaways we got from both setups and highlight the best and worst performing models in this study.

4.1 Single Slice Classification

4.1.1 Leaderboard Approach

Fig. 4.1 shows the distribution of the rankings of the models on all four metrics for both All (others) data and Valid (others) data arranged via the median from the best (rank 1) to the worst (rank 8). All (others) data refers to both the datasets in conflict and not in conflict with the model as discussed in Chapter 3 excluding its own dataset, while Valid (others) data refers to datasets not in conflict with the model, also excluding its own dataset.

Best Models. Majority, for both All (others) and Valid (others), COVID Net CT-2 S ranks the best. However, it should be noted that for All (others), it has the majority of the conflicts and for Valid (others), it is only evaluated on three datasets. The second best performing model is COVID NET CT-1 S and to recall as well, it is the only model that does not have any conflicts with any datasets.

Worst Models. If we consider the All (others) data, the worst ranking model is different for each metric but ResNet50V2 and DenseNet-169 are mostly seen in the bottom three. For Valid (others), the most frequent models in the bottom three are ResNet50V2 + FPN, Xception, and ResNet50V2.

Figure 4.1: Single Slice Classification - ranking across four metrics considering all and valid data. The models are arranged using the median of the ranking distribution from the best (rank 1) to the worst (rank 8). In the majority of the rankings, COVID Net CT-2 S ranks the best.

Table 4.1: Single Slice Classification - results of evaluation metrics**(a) Accuracy**

Models	SARS-CoV-2		COVID-CT	COVIDx	COVIDx	COVID-	COVIDx	Self	All		Valid		Invalid		
	Ct-scan	iCTCF	UC San Diego	CT-1	CT-2	CTset	CO-IRv2		CT-3	Mean others	Percent Change	Mean others	Percent Change	Mean others	Percent Change
1. DenseNet121	93.16	81.79	48.28	62.06	63.57	94.45	92.18	65.13	93.16	72.49	-22.19	73.4	-21.21	70.23	-24.61
2. Self-Trans	56.14	57.47	85.22	47.77	46.56	32.35	52.76	45.65	85.22	48.39	-43.22	40.06	-52.99	51.72	-39.31
3. DenseNet169	50.7	56.81	77.83	58.16	58.63	25.61	50.71	62.54	77.83	51.88	-33.34	41.89	-46.18	55.88	-28.2
4. ResNet50V2 + FPN	45.07	71.39	51.72	79.4	76.47	98.7	49.62	76.56	98.7	64.32	-34.83	59.44	-39.78	76.52	-22.47
5. Xception	44.67	71.37	52.22	79.49	76.55	98.11	49.46	76.63	98.11	64.34	-34.42	59.44	-39.41	76.59	-21.93
6. ResNet50V2	45.27	69.65	51.72	73.47	71.67	98.16	49.5	72.86	98.16	62.02	-36.82	57.92	-40.99	72.27	-26.38
7. COVID-Net CT-1 S	45.88	74.47	60.1	96.22	91.04	94.45	50.67	88.42	96.22	72.15	-25.02	72.15	-25.02	N/A	N/A
8. COVID-Net CT-2 S	62.78	82.73	63.55	97.6	97.27	5.55	59.29	96.49	97.27	66.86	-31.26	85.62	-11.98	52.78	-45.74

(b) AUC

Models	SARS-CoV-2		COVID-CT	COVIDx	COVIDx	COVID-	COVIDx	Self	All		Valid		Invalid		
	Ct-scan	iCTCF	UC San Diego	CT-1	CT-2	CTset	CO-IRv2		CT-3	Mean others	Percent Change	Mean others	Percent Change	Mean others	Percent Change
1. DenseNet121	97.61	91.42	50.52	50.59	55.46	69.14	97.4	58.22	97.61	67.54	-30.81	64.97	-33.44	73.96	-24.23
2. Self-Trans	53.25	69.79	94.02	82.88	71.79	41.55	53.51	69.09	94.02	63.12	-32.87	62.22	-33.82	63.49	-32.47
3. DenseNet169	52.12	51.11	85.86	90.78	76.06	58.89	49.74	68.35	85.86	63.86	-25.62	74.84	-12.83	59.48	-30.72
4. ResNet50V2 + FPN	38.49	48.09	32.59	40.65	39.6	98.56	36.96	37.94	98.56	39.19	-60.24	39.36	-60.06	38.77	-60.66
5. Xception	54.45	75.1	59.38	65.06	63.22	99.25	54.61	60.54	99.25	61.77	-37.76	61.72	-37.81	61.88	-37.65
6. ResNet50V2	39.83	39.49	50.48	57.37	54.82	99.13	34.31	52.7	99.13	47	-52.59	44.3	-55.31	53.76	-45.77
7. COVID-Net CT-1 S	36.99	62.77	63	99.43	96.13	59.81	35.2	94	99.43	63.99	-35.64	63.99	-35.64	N/A	N/A
8. COVID-Net CT-2 S	68.51	92.62	65.76	99.59	99.44	59.95	66.69	98.94	99.44	78.87	-20.69	89.01	-10.49	71.26	-28.34

(c) F1-Score

Models	SARS-CoV-2		COVID-CT	COVIDx	COVIDx	COVID-	COVIDx	Self	All		Valid		Invalid		
	Ct-scan	iCTCF	UC San Diego	CT-1	CT-2	CTset	CO-IRv2		CT-3	Mean others	Percent Change	Mean others	Percent Change	Mean others	Percent Change
1. DenseNet121	93.17	82.57	44.15	64.25	64.51	91.75	92.18	65.94	93.17	72.19	-22.52	73.8	-20.79	68.17	-26.83
2. Self-Trans	44.17	59.19	85.19	50.21	48.61	44.29	41	47.56	85.19	47.86	-43.82	47.25	-44.54	48.11	-43.53
3. DenseNet169	49.86	58.36	77.73	61.51	61.67	34.54	49.34	65.31	77.73	54.37	-30.05	48.03	-38.21	56.91	-26.79
4. ResNet50V2 + FPN	28.58	59.48	35.27	70.36	66.34	98.74	33.35	66.46	98.74	51.41	-47.93	45.41	-54.01	66.4	-32.75
5. Xception	27.71	59.46	36.36	70.41	66.38	98.23	32.86	66.49	98.23	51.38	-47.69	45.36	-53.82	66.44	-32.36
6. ResNet50V2	28.67	58.89	36.12	71.92	68.4	98.27	33.02	68.38	98.27	52.2	-46.88	45.72	-53.48	68.39	-30.41
7. COVID-Net CT-1 S	30.94	66.47	52.98	96.08	90.26	91.75	35.93	86.98	96.08	65.04	-32.31	65.04	-32.31	N/A	N/A
8. COVID-Net CT-2 S	62.73	83.39	63.28	97.57	97.24	0.58	59.2	96.47	97.24	66.17	-31.95	85.59	-11.98	51.61	-46.93

(d) Precision

Models	SARS-CoV-2		COVID-CT	COVIDx	COVIDx	COVID-	COVIDx	Self	All		Valid		Invalid		
	Ct-scan	iCTCF	UC San Diego	CT-1	CT-2	CTset	CO-IRv2		CT-3	Mean others	Percent Change	Mean others	Percent Change	Mean others	Percent Change
1. DenseNet121	93.34	86.32	48.92	67.11	65.63	89.21	92.2	66.89	93.34	73.75	-20.99	75.03	-19.62	70.56	-24.41
2. Self-Trans	58.13	70.87	85.97	81.7	72.45	87.27	61.32	72.3	85.97	72.01	-16.24	84.49	-1.72	67.01	-22.05
3. DenseNet169	52.91	60.86	78.08	83.76	74.85	91.37	50.71	72.27	78.08	69.53	-10.95	87.57	12.15	62.32	-20.18
4. ResNet50V2 + FPN	56.92	79.57	26.75	63.17	58.58	98.81	53.99	58.71	98.81	56.81	-42.51	56.08	-43.24	58.65	-40.64
5. Xception	20.08	50.95	75.16	63.19	58.59	98.55	37.13	58.72	98.55	51.97	-47.27	49.3	-49.97	58.66	-40.48
6. ResNet50V2	75.34	52.93	50.9	70.76	66.65	98.55	46.16	66.48	98.55	61.32	-37.78	59.22	-39.91	66.57	-32.45
7. COVID-Net CT-1 S	60.41	79.24	71.29	96.39	91.89	89.21	64.77	89.73	96.39	78.08	-19	78.08	-19	N/A	N/A
8. COVID-Net CT-2 S	62.7	85.93	63.63	97.6	97.26	0.31	59.33	96.46	97.26	66.57	-31.55	85.59	-12	52.3	-46.23

Changes in Performance Rate. Table 4.1 shows the breakdown of the values along with the mean scores and percent changes of each model performance for All (others), Valid (others), and Invalid (others) data-model matchups. All of the performance percent changes went down for all of the models.

Assumption of Overly Optimistic Performance Due to Data Leakage. To complement Table 4.1, Fig 4.2 shows the arrangements of the percent changes for the mean others of *All*, *Valid*, and *Invalid* data-model matchups. With the assumption of overly optimistic performance due to data leakage, the expected order of the model performance from highest to lowest performance is *Invalid*, *All*, and *Valid* data-model matchups. This is due to the fact that *Invalid* mean scores are calculated on those datasets in conflict with the model, i.e. in which the samples are leaked during the model's development. *All* comes second since it is the mix of *Invalid* and *Valid*, and lastly, *Valid* since it is calculated from datasets not in conflict with the model. However, Fig 4.2 shows that this is not always the case. The *Valid* and *Invalid* places usually switch places. COVID-Net CT-2 S had them switched in all four metrics while Densenet121 had them switched in Accuracy, F1-Score and Precision. Most switches occur in AUC with three models: DenseNet169, ResNet50V2 + FPN, and COVID-Net CT-2 S. The reason behind the switching seems to have to do with the degree of data leakage and how that data got learned by the model since some of the works reported that they curated the original datasets before forming the Frankenstein datasets.

Figure 4.2: Single Slice Classification - differences of percentages in Self, All (mean others), Invalid (mean others) and Valid (mean others) across Accuracy, AUC, F1-Score, and Precision.

4.1.2 Beyond the Leaderboard

Deconstructed Confusion Matrix and Predicted Probability Distribution For Fine-grained Analysis.

Fig 4.3 and Fig 4.4 show the details behind the summarized performance metrics in 4.1.1. In Fig 4.3, it shows that most models did worse on detecting the COVID class rather than the NONCOVID class. Models that performed worse on the COVID class are ResNet50V2 + FPN, Xception, and ResNet50V2. These models are the ones trained in a 16-bit TIFF. For the NONCOVID class, Self-Trans noticeably performed the worst. However, there are cases where the model performed worse on the COVID class but performed greatly on the NONCOVID class. There are interesting behaviors as well given the totally wrong(100 for TN, 0 for FP) and totally right (100 for TP, 0 for FN) scores which occur when the model is evaluated using COVID-CTset and the models trained on COVID-CTset on other datasets. This behavior was not obvious when we used the evaluation metrics in 4.1.1.

Figure 4.3: Single Slice Classification - deconstructed confusion matrix. The following TP, FN, TN, and FP in percentage are given such that *the darker the values on all of them, the better the performance* (the opposite holds true as well). Model results on its own dataset were marked with *white* and the data-model conflicts are marked with *red*.

Figure 4.4: Single Slice Classification - predicted probability distribution of TP, FN, TN, and FP.

Fig 4.4 further digs on the distribution of TP, FN, TN, and FP. The ideal behavior is to be confidently right (for TP and TN) and to be not confidently wrong (for FN and FP). In other words, we want the correct distributions to be gearing towards 1 for TP and 0 for TN and the wrong distributions, both FN and FP, to be gearing near 0.5, i.e. downwards to the 0.5 mark for FP and upwards the 0.5 mark for FN. It is dangerous to have models that are confidently wrong. Among them, there are three interesting models: DenseNet-169 is both confidently right and wrong; ResNet50V2 is NOT both confidently right and wrong; COVID-Net CT-2 S is confidently right and not confidently wrong even in the datasets not in conflict with the model–SARS-CoV-2 CT-scan, COVIDx CT-1, and COVIDx CT-3 datasets. The model with the same behavior is DenseNet121. The remaining models are usually confidently right in terms of either TP or TN and some are confidently wrong via FN but not confidently wrong looking at FP.

Reliability Assessments via Model Calibration. Given the models trained on its own dataset, the ones near the perfect calibration line are DenseNet121 with SARS-CoV-2 CT-scan, and COVID-Net CT-2 S with COVIDx CT-2. The most disastrous results come from COVID-CTset where the models (ResNet50V2 + FPN, Xception, and ResNet50V2) trained on it are nowhere near the perfect

calibration line. Self-trans and DenseNet169 do not appear to be near the perfect calibration line as well with COVID-CT Dataset UC San Diego. On the other hand, models that appear near the perfect calibration line outside their own dataset are COVID-Net CT-2 S on COVIDx CT-1 (which is better than COVID-Net CT-1 S which was trained on COVIDx CT-1), and COVIDx CT-3 which it may be argued that there are still similarities on COVIDx CT-2; and DenseNet121 with CO-IRv2 which can be attributed to having DenseNet121’s dataset as a subset of CO-IRv2.

In Fig. 4.6, we look at the correlation of ECE and the classification errors extending it to the four metrics. This is an extension of the question [101] had given but only for accuracy: “Given two models, one more accurate and the other better calibrated, which should a practitioner choose?” Most of the models follow a positive correlation, i.e. a better performing model has lower calibration error, which is mostly true in terms of Accuracy and F1-Score. However, for AUC and Precision, negative correlations are observed for models not trained in their own datasets. This means that models that perform well looking *only* on AUC and Precision may show higher calibration errors. This is seen with COVIDx CT-1, CT-2, and CT-3.

Figure 4.5: Reliability diagrams (bins=5).

Figure 4.6: ECE using L1 norm and classification errors across four metrics (bins=5).

Where the Model Looks for COVID-19 on Average. Fig 4.7 highlights the averaged outcomes of Grad-CAM for each model given a dataset. With this, we have a way to understand where the model usually looks for COVID and also its similarities or differences in terms of the behavior against the original model trained on that data.

We can observe that the majority of the results for unseen datasets is very similar to the result where the model is trained on its own dataset, i.e. the area where the model looks on its own dataset is *most likely* where it will look on other datasets. Though there are cases where it can be very different such as the results in COVID-Net CT-1 S and CT-2 S on SARS-COV-2 Ct-Scan and CO-IRv2 where it looks mostly on the outer side rather than on the middle parts.

Some results look similar to other results which may be due to two reasons. First, the datasets are tagged with conflicts (e.g. SARS-COV-2 Ct-Scan and CO-IRv2) and the presence of similar samples on the datasets are high. Second, for those without conflicts, the datasets are from the same distribution (e.g. COVIDx series of datasets).

Figure 4.7: Averaged Grad-CAM results for the true positive outcomes or the correctly predicted COVID samples for Single Slice Classification. The data-model conflicts are marked with a *red box* and the results from models trained on its own dataset are marked with a *black box*. It should be noted for interpretation that some of the samples may have slight variations (e.g. rotations, shifts, zooms).

Looking by the columns, we get the insights on the different behaviors of different models (which may be trained or not trained on that data) on one dataset. Strikingly, there are cases where different models that are trained on the same data have different behaviors. For example, for models trained in COVID-CT UC San Diego, Self-Trans and DenseNet-169, both have DenseNet-169 backbones with the only difference in weight initialization, behaved differently in detecting COVID-19. This is noticeable as well for models trained in COVID-CTset. Their best model, ResNet50V2 + FPN behaved way different against ResNet50V2 and Xception, whereas ResNet50V2 and Xception's behavior are rather similar.

4.2 Multiple Slice Classification

4.2.1 Leaderboard Approach

Fig 4.8 shows the arranged ranking via the median from best (rank 1) to the worst (rank 5). All (others) data refers to both the datasets in conflict and not in conflict with the model as discussed in Chapter 3 excluding its own dataset while Valid (others) data refers to datasets not in conflict with the model, also excluding its own dataset.

Best Models. For All (others) data, Deep Wilcoxon tops for both Accuracy and Precision while TAC - ResNet14 tops for both AUC and F1-Score. For the Valid (others), Deep Wilcoxon still tops Accuracy and also tops F1-Score this time while TAC-ResNet14 tops AUC and Precision.

Worst Models. Consistently, the group trained in COVID-CTset performed the worst, specifically, Xception, ResNet50V2 and ResNet50V2 + FPN at times switched the rankings in the bottom three.

Figure 4.8: Multiple Slice Classification - ranking across four metrics considering all data and valid data excluding the dataset where the model is trained. The models are arranged using the median of the ranking distribution from the best (rank 1) to the worst (rank 5). In the majority of the rankings, both Deep Wilcoxon and TAC - ResNet14 ranked the best.

Changes in Performance Rate. Almost all of them decreased in performance in all unseen data for All, Valid, and Invalid except TAC - ResNet14 in Accuracy for the Invalid part. However, there are gaps in the tables since we did not have access to the original dataset for Deep Wilcoxon and TAC - ResNet14. The only matching metric to our metrics that were released is Accuracy.

Assumption of Overly Optimistic Performance Due to Data Leakage. The expected order from highest to lowest performance is still the same as with Single Slice Classification which is *Self*, *Invalid*, *All*, and *Valid*. This order is followed by most of the four models with only TAC - ResNet14 performing differently for Accuracy where *Self* and *Invalid* are switched, and AUC where *Invalid* and *Valid* are switched. Even though there is a conflict with TAC - ResNet14 and COVID-CTset (the only dataset it has conflict with), the reason for the switching shows not to be from the data leakage, but looks like rather due to the data mismatch, as we can see in the deconstructed confusion matrix in the next part that it has the behavior of really low TP and really high TN. However, we will confirm this further in *4.3 General Discussions*.

Table 4.2: Multiple Slice Classification - results of evaluation metrics

(a) Accuracy

Models	New SARS-COV-2	MosMed Data	ZAFFINO Dataset	COVID-CTset	COVID-CT-MD	MAFTOUNI	DataBiox HRCTv1	Self	All		Valid		Invalid	
									Mean others	Percent change	Mean others	Percent change	Mean others	Percent change
1. Deep Wilcoxon	82.38	48.26	83.87	6.67	68.85	63.64	47.97	91.9	57.38	-37.56	57.38	-37.56	-	-
2. TAC - ResNet14	78.57	12.21	31.18	92.16	74.1	72.37	18.27	85	54.12	-36.33	47.78	-43.79	92.16	8.42
3. ResNet50V2 + FPN	62.86	11.05	0	97.25	40	56.06	5.84	97.25	29.3	-69.87	23.95	-75.37	56.06	-42.35
4. Xception	60	0	0	93.33	44.59	58.73	5.84	93.33	28.19	-69.8	22.09	-76.33	58.73	-37.07
5. ResNet50V2	60	0	0	93.73	44.59	58.91	15.48	93.73	29.83	-68.17	24.01	-74.38	58.91	-37.15

*As reported from validation set

(b) AUC

Models	New SARS-COV-2	MosMed Data	ZAFFINO Dataset	COVID-CTset	COVID-CT-MD	MAFTOUNI	DataBiox HRCTv1	Self	All		Valid		Invalid	
									Mean others	Percent change	Mean others	Percent change	Mean others	Percent change
1. Deep Wilcoxon	77.12	-	-	42.09	70.74	56.67	56.06	-	60.54	-	60.54	-	-	-
2. TAC - ResNet14	74.76	-	-	57.28	73.76	69.9	60	-	67.14	-	69.61	-	57.28	-
3. ResNet50V2 + FPN	51.25	-	-	95.96	44.42	47.99	50	95.96	48.42	-49.54	48.56	-49.4	47.99	-49.99
4. Xception	48.7	-	-	93.85	50	50.11	50	93.85	49.7	-47.04	49.57	-47.18	50.11	-46.61
5. ResNet50V2	48.46	-	-	94.06	50	50.32	55.12	94.06	50.98	-45.8	51.19	-45.58	50.32	-46.5

(c) F1-Score

Models	New SARS-COV-2	MosMed Data	ZAFFINO Dataset	COVID-CTset	COVID-CT-MD	MAFTOUNI	DataBiox HRCTv1	Self	All		Valid		Invalid	
									Mean others	Percent change	Mean others	Percent change	Mean others	Percent change
1. Deep Wilcoxon	80.96	-	-	2.33	68.21	55.66	60	-	53.43	-	53.43	-	-	-
2. TAC - ResNet14	77.75	-	-	90.73	74.09	71.66	23.02	-	67.45	-	61.63	-	90.73	-
3. ResNet50V2 + FPN	49.48	-	-	97.41	28.34	43	0.64	97.41	30.37	-68.82	26.15	-73.15	43	-55.86
4. Xception	47.22	-	-	94.2	27.5	43.56	0.64	94.2	29.73	-68.44	25.12	-73.33	43.56	-53.76
5. ResNet50V2	46.43	-	-	94.51	27.5	43.96	18.21	94.51	34.03	-63.99	30.71	-67.51	43.96	-53.49

(d) Precision

Models	New SARS-COV-2	MosMed Data	ZAFFINO Dataset	COVID-CTset	COVID-CT-MD	MAFTOUNI	DataBiox HRCTv1	Self	All		Valid		Invalid	
									Mean others	Percent change	Mean others	Percent change	Mean others	Percent change
1. Deep Wilcoxon	85.65	-	-	37.6	73.93	69.21	90.44	-	71.37	-	71.37	-	-	-
2. TAC - ResNet14	78.72	-	-	89.94	74.08	72.22	92.69	-	81.53	-	79.43	-	89.94	-
3. ResNet50V2 + FPN	76.79	-	-	97.76	31.33	39.85	0.34	97.76	37.08	-62.07	36.15	-63.02	39.85	-59.24
4. Xception	44.28	-	-	96.16	19.88	75.78	0.34	96.16	35.07	-63.53	21.5	-77.64	75.78	-21.19
5. ResNet50V2	37.86	-	-	96.27	19.88	75.84	94.54	96.27	57.03	-40.76	50.76	-47.27	75.84	-21.22

Figure 4.9: Multiple Slice Classification - differences of percentages in Self, All (mean others), Invalid (mean others) and Valid (mean others) across Accuracy, AUC, F1-Score, and Precision.

4.2.2 Beyond the Leaderboard

Figure 4.10: Multiple Slice Classification - deconstructed confusion matrix. The following TP, FN, TN, and FP in percentage are given such that *the darker the values on all of them, the better the performance* (the opposite holds true as well). Model results on its own dataset were marked with *white* and the data-model conflicts are marked with *red*.

Deconstructed Confusion Matrix for Fine-grained Analysis. Fig 4.10 shows that the majority of the models struggle in predicting the COVID class. Even with this, it is notable that Deep Wilcoxon both have an over 80 score on unseen data and TAC - ResNet14 have an over 76 score for true positives. It also shows that these two models have a good performance for the NONCOVID class except in COVID-CTset data. On the other hand, similar to the behavior seen in Single Class Classification, ResNet50V2 + FPN, Xception, and ResNet50V2 have the behavior extremes when tested with other datasets as well as other models when tested on COVID-CTset.

4.3 General Discussions

4.3.1 Is the behavior of COVID-CTset models to other datasets (and vice versa) caused by the image formats creating a data mismatch?

With this question we look at the problem first. First is with testing other models trained on three-channel data on COVID-CTset which is a 16-bit TIFF and second is with testing the models trained in COVID-CTset with other datasets.

For the first setup, there are two ways in which the models trained in three channels can accept the one channel data. The first one is to just follow the original input schemes of the systems—which we did in 4.1 and 4.2. Fig 4.11 shows two input schemes—reading using cv2 and using PIL—the models used to accept the COVID-CTset data and how it looks after it was read. Reading using cv2, the image is almost completely black. One can only see the image structure if we stare intently or enlarge the image. Reading using PIL, on the other hand, caused the image to increase in brightness. The second way is to accept the PNG version of the COVID-CTset data. In this case, reading with both cv2 and reading with PIL visually output the same and expected image.

Figure 4.11: Reading the COVID-CTset data using cv2 and PIL for both TIF and PNG versions.

Table 4.3 shows the results of other models on both single and multiple slice classification tested on both TIFF and PNG versions. With only looking at the TIFF version in the deconstructed confusion matrices above, the suggestion that we get is that there is a data mismatch due to the image formats. However, the table shows that even with testing with PNG, the behavior still persists. This means that it is not a data mismatch due to the image format but with the data composition itself.

Table 4.3: Results of other models from Single and Multiple Slice Classification on TIFF and PNG versions of COVID-CTset dataset.

Single Slice	Trained		TIFF				PNG			
	on	Input	tp (%)	fn (%)	tn (%)	fp (%)	tp (%)	fn (%)	tn (%)	fp (%)
1. DenseNet121	PNG	cv2	0	100	100	0	0	100	99.85	0.15
2. Self-Trans	PNG	PIL	54.98	45.02	31.02	68.98	19.91	80.09	84.97	15.03
3. DenseNet169	PNG	PIL	85.93	14.07	22.06	77.94	0	100	99.29	0.71
7. COVID-Net CT-1 S	PNG	cv2	0	100	100	0	3.55	96.45	95.09	4.91
8. COVID-Net CT-2 S	PNG	cv2	100	0	0	100	22.13	77.87	74.34	25.66
Multiple Slice										
1. Deep Wilcoxon	unknown	cv2	83.33	16.67	0.84	99.16	27.78	72.22	98.31	1.69
2. TAC - ResNet14	JPG	autogluon	16.67	83.33	97.89	2.11	61.11	38.89	88.61	11.39

For the second setup, Table 4.4 shows that the behavior of COVID-CTset models to other datasets is due to data mismatch because of the image format. COVID-CTset models are able to accept three-channel data by converting the three-channel data into one-channel via grayscale. With this, the extreme behavior of having an almost perfect FN and TN shows up when it is tested on the PNG version.

Table 4.4: Comparison of COVID-CTset model performance on its own data in TIFF and PNG versions. To satisfy the channel requirements of the model, the PNG version is converted to one channel by converting the image to grayscale using OpenCV.

	TIF				PNG			
	tp (%)	fn (%)	tn (%)	fp (%)	tp (%)	fn (%)	tn (%)	fp (%)
1. ResNet50V2 + FPN	94.44	5.56	97.47	2.53	5.56	94.44	90.3	9.7
2. Xception	94.44	5.56	93.25	6.75	0	100	100	0
3. ResNet50V2	94.44	5.56	93.67	6.33	0	100	100	0

With this, the rule of thumb observed to be followed by most studies is to use the same image formats for both the development and production stage to avoid any kinds of data mismatch. However, this impairs flexibility or adaptability. A study from [105] treated image compression as one of the image transformations or distortions and concluded that “the networks are more sensitive to changes in blur and noise compared with compression and contrast”. They used JPEG and JPEG 2000. Our hypothesis is that this is not contradictory with our findings since the key solution would involve

understanding how aggressive the image transformation on the image values since the models work in pixel-level afterall, i.e. even if the images look the same, they may be represented in a very different way in the pixel level. This is suggested to be investigated for future work since this case of having many image formats is prominent in medical applications.

4.3.2 Does the data leakage assumption of leading to overly optimistic performance hold?

Data leakage does not always lead to *overly* optimistic performance. It varies on the degree of the leakage which may have resulted from either data curation or data collection. For data curation, some of the Frankenstein datasets reported the curation of their data, which means some samples were disregarded. With this, the data leakage against the original dataset is not full but still with a high degree. For data collection, a good example is COVID-CT UC San Diego dataset. Since they only got the images from papers, very few of the samples per each dataset may have been taken *unless the papers attached all or most of the image samples*. We can see this just by looking at the percentage drop with the metrics and the switching of the places from Fig 4.2 of Invalid and Valid places for DenseNet169 and almost close values for All, Valid and Invalid for Self-Trans.

4.3.3 Do the internal model rankings change during external validation?

This question refers to the case where you have models trained on the same dataset, ranked them, and based on the internal test set, the best model gets the spotlight and gets used on other or new datasets. However, this is not the case as we saw for Single Slice Classification, taking Self-Trans and DenseNet169, the rankings changed as well as for Multiple Slice Classification with Deep Wilcoxon and TAC - ResNet14. This means that the declared best model is highly constrained by the internal test set which is supposed to reflect the data distribution it will receive in the future based on the identical and independent data (i.i.d) assumption which is often violated in practice [106,108]. With out-of-distribution data, the rankings in the internal dataset may not hold as we saw from our results. In short, this points to the rethinking of the selection of the best model for production and the discarding of the lower ranking models.

4.3.4 The Promising and the Worst Works

Selecting these models are highly dependent on the datasets and other models collected. We define *promising works* as the works we suggest to be further investigated to understand and see its performance on other datasets or local datasets when chosen to be adapted on a system, and for further improvement, while *worst works* are works that are hard to control or cause extreme behaviors.

For the Single Slice Classification, we put forward COVID-Net CT-2 S, COVID-Net CT-1 S, and Self-Trans. The first two ranked consistently as the first and second best on the metric rankings. Looking at the confusion metrics, even if Self-Trans have a number of conflicts, we should recall that the degree of data leakage is low. We suggest that if the metadata containing the sample names is

completed by the authors, to test it on a clean version and also test it on new datasets not in conflict with COVID-CT UC San Diego data. The first and last model also show some potential on detecting the COVID class and the second model on detecting the NONCOVID class based on the deconstructed confusion matrix. These three also show that they are confidently right on their predictions and not confidently wrong as seen in the predicted probability distribution. With calibration, the first two did mostly well as they are near the perfect calibration line with their own datasets and other datasets in the COVIDx dataset series. We suggest applying calibration techniques to improve the calibration.

For Multiple Slice Classification, Deep Wilcoxon and TAC - ResNet14 did well on the rankings and detecting the NONCOVID class but still needs to be improved in detecting the COVID class.

For the worst models for both single and multiple slices, we suggest taking caution on using the models trained in COVID-CTset as we saw that it is highly dependent on the data type it takes in. If we are able to convert the data to the 16-bit TIFF data type, we can further understand its behavior; however, the authors did not release any documentation on how to specifically convert or produce the same data type. We see that as the authors put forward the novelty of the dataset type but without the documentation, the data matching and usability suffers.

5 CONCLUSION

5.1 Evaluation

In this report, we focused on the evaluation of different datasets and models for COVID-19 recognition under the binary classification task using 2D chest CT images. This is motivated by two opposing sides: the increasing number of datasets and works in this area proving the performance of their systems and the critical reviews and appraisals which use qualitative approaches giving feedbacks such as “none of the models identified are of potential clinical use” and that the works are not directly comparable with each other [13-15].

In Chapter 3, we covered the materials and methods discussing five sections. The first section covers the dataset and model collection which shows that the information about data splits is the key in enabling comparison between studies and emphasizes that the main challenge for the models is reproducibility. In the second section, we introduced the Single and Multiple Slice Classification as subtasks such that the main difference between them is the influence of slices in the final result. For the third and fourth section, we both discussed in detail the datasets and models for both subtasks. For datasets, we explored the basic characteristics, origins, demographics, and data split breakdown and distribution percentage along with the data conflicts such as varying label definition, data leakage, and frankenstein datasets. For the models, we covered the initial reproducibility test; summarized each

model's training and testing procedures; gave comments on reproducibility for testing; and finally, discussed the model conflicts. Then, we summarized the effects of conflicts on evaluation using a data-model conflict chart. In the last section, we discussed our evaluation methodology which was divided into two: the leaderboard approach and beyond the leaderboard, in which the results were discussed in the next chapter.

In Chapter 4, we discussed the results for the leaderboard and beyond the leaderboard sections for both Single and Multiple Slice Classification, then distilled the takeaways via general discussions.

The leaderboard approach ranks each model against one another based on the common metrics such as Accuracy, AUC, F1-Score (weighted), and Precision (weighted). We also observed the model's performance under the conflicts by categorizing them into *Self*, *All*, *Invalid*, and *Valid* data-model matchups. We found that the ideal ordering under the data leakage assumption of overly optimistic performance (i.e. *Self*, *Invalid*, *All*, and *Valid*) was not followed by some models and further looked into this in the general discussions.

Beyond the leaderboard, we zoomed into the details behind the metrics and saw whether the models are confidently right, wrong, or neither, using the deconstructed confusion matrix and predicted probability distribution. We also assessed the calibration of the models using reliability diagrams and ECE which was further compared to the classification errors using the four metrics. With this, we found that most of the models are not calibrated on their own and external datasets which suggests the need for calibration. Lastly, we introduced the averaging of Grad-CAM results to view the global behavior of each model per dataset. We observed that where the model looks on unseen dataset is very similar to the areas it has looked on its own dataset, and that the heatmaps can also support in showing whether there are conflicts between datasets or the datasets are from the same distribution. Also, strikingly, we noticed that even if two models were trained on the same dataset, they can have very different averaged Grad-CAM results.

For general discussions, we covered four parts. The first part answers the question: *Is the behavior of COVID-CTset models to other datasets (and vice versa) caused by the image formats creating a data mismatch?* We tested the models on both PNG and TIFF versions of COVID-CTset data and concluded that it is not a data mismatch problem due to the image format but rather the data composition itself. On the other hand, applying the COVID-CTset models to other datasets causes data mismatch due to image format since the models did well on the TIFF version of their own dataset and did poorly on the PNG version. For the second part, we ask: *Does the data leakage assumption of leading to overly optimistic performance hold?* From the results, we observed that the overly optimistic effect of data leakage varies on the degree of the leakage which may have resulted from either data curation or collection. The third part asks: *Do the internal model rankings change during external validation?* We found that the internal model ranking does not hold on external datasets. This

raises concern on rethinking the selection of the best model for deployment and the discarding of the lower ranking models decided from the internal dataset. Lastly, we highlighted the promising and the worst models. We put forward promising models for further investigation and improvement, and worst models for the users to take caution in using them. For Single Slice Classification, we have COVID-Net CT-2 S and CT-1 S, and Self-Trans and for Multiple Slice Classification, we have Deep Wilcoxon and TAC - ResNet14. These models either ranked highly in the leaderboard approach, detected the COVID or NONCOVID class well, showed that they were confidently right and not confidently wrong, or nearly calibrated. On the other hand, the worst performing models for both classification tasks are ResNet50V2 + FPN, Xception, and ResNet50V2. These models are susceptible to data mismatch, and extreme outcomes (i.e. having near 100 TP, FN, TN, or FP). We provided a global view of the models' behavior using averaged Grad-CAM to further understand these behaviors.

5.2 Future Work

We discuss the potential future directions for both Single and Multiple Slice Classification.

a.) Effect of different image representations on modern neural networks. In the general discussion, we asked whether the extreme behavior outcomes on COVID-CTset (both the models and the dataset) is an effect of data mismatch. We concluded that when other models are applied to the dataset, it is not a mismatch due to image format but when the COVID-CTset models are applied to other image formats, it is a data mismatch problem due to the image format. Since different image formats are used in medical applications, the effect of these transformations on modern neural networks can be further explored, i.e. *how sensitive are modern neural networks to these changes?*

b.) Application of model calibration techniques. [13, 100, 101] discusses the importance of calibrating models for high-stake applications such as in the medical area, and that modern neural networks are susceptible to miscalibration despite reporting high performance in the metrics. In Chapter 4, we saw that though some of the models are nearly calibrated, most of them are not. [100] and [101] discussed some techniques calibrating the models such as Temperature Scaling, Binning methods, Isotonic Regression, Platt Scaling, and Matrix and Vector Scaling.

c.) Further investigation of multiple slice classification. Since the works in multiple slice classification only came out recently, only few works have investigated this approach. We encourage further investigation in this area especially in handling and analyzing multiple slice images for model development. We also recommend improvements on the labeling of the data, i.e. in Chapter 3, we saw that most of the datasets have a patient-level labeling instead of slice-level labeling. Along with this, we suggest veering away from binary outputs and leave an option to explore the probabilities to give a continuous prediction information of the patient having COVID-19. These will also enable better and fine-grained analyses since the current test information was not informative enough and had hindered

us from automatically looking in detail as seen in Chapter 4.

d.) Investigation and approaches to distribution shifts. Each work we considered in this study follows the independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) assumption in their development phase. As [99,106-108] argues, this is usually violated in practice and more of an active research area rather than seeing it as a failure from the works. Numerous types of distribution shifts exist but the main three types are Covariate or Feature Shift, Semantic or Label Shift, and Concept Drift [99,106-108]. We have touched into this very lightly in Appendix C and in our analyses focusing more on Covariate Shift. Specifically in Appendix C, we used UMAP to understand the differences in the distribution of our dataset: *Is the data still considered in-distribution or is it out-of-distribution already? How different are the datasets from one another?* However, this is limited visually, especially if the dataset is large, since we cannot see the other datasets clearly. In addition, looking into the detection of these shifts can help complementing or even removing dependencies on metadata since most medical data are anonymized for the development phase; and dependencies on the ground truth data for the evaluation and monitoring phase. It can also inform the model building or updating process. Another type of shift we uncovered is the varying label definition which can be classified under Semantic or Label shift but we have not touched into the extent to see how it affects the performance of the system. Other types of shifts may still be concealed. Shift or OOD detection [107] and adaptation algorithms [108] can be further explored in this direction to cope with these issues.

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APPENDIX A

DISCREPANCIES FROM THE ORIGINAL RESULTS

The discrepancies were only observed in Single Slice Classification for works that did not release the models and were retrained using the released code. We observed that these discrepancies came from the uncontrolled randomness present in the data augmentation stage.

Table A.1: Discrepancies from Original Results for Single Slice Classification

Model	Original	Used	Metric
1. DenseNet121*	92.35	93.16	Accuracy
2. Self-Trans	86	85.22	Accuracy
	94	94.02	AUC
	85	85.19	F1-Score
3. DenseNet169*	84.7	77.83	Accuracy
	91.9	85.86	AUC
	85.4	77.73	F1-Score
4. ResNet50V2 + FPN	98.7	98.7	Accuracy
	98.81	98.81	Precision
5. Xception	98.11	98.11	Accuracy
	98.55	98.55	Precision
6. ResNet50V2	98.16	98.16	Accuracy
	98.55	98.55	Precision
7. **COVID-Net CT-1 S	93.2	91.04	Accuracy
8. COVID-Net CT-2 S	98.3	97.27	Accuracy

*Retrained ** On COVIDx CT-2 data

Discrepancies are highlighted

No discrepancies were observed from the Multiple Slice Classification for the COVID-CTset models. For Deep Wilcoxon and TAC - ResNet14, we cannot check the replicated system against the original results since the dataset where they were trained was not acquired. Though upon checking, they released the exact weights and there is no randomness present in the inference code that can change the results from the original.

APPENDIX B

TOTAL PARAMETERS AND FLOPS

Table B.1: Total Number of Parameters and FLOPS for Single Slice Classification

	Params (K)	FLOPS (G)
1. DenseNet121	7,306	0.467
2. Self-Trans	14,149.48	6.84
3. DenseNet169	14,149.48	6.84
4. ResNet50V2 + FPN	34,058.66	40.9
5. Xception	21,909.48	47.9
6. ResNet50V2	24,607.11	35.7
7. COVID-Net CT-1 S	447.57	1.94
8. COVID-Net CT-2 S	447.57	1.94

Table B.2: Total Number of Parameters and FLOPS for Multiple Slice Classification. We were not able to get the total parameters and FLOPS of TAC - ResNet14 as the information is not released and we were not able to find a way to extract it from the released model using AutoML.

Models	Params (K)	FLOPS (G)
1. Deep Wilcoxon	27,496.80	8.72
2. TAC - ResNet14	-	-
4. ResNet50V2 + FPN	34,058.66	40.9
5. Xception	21,909.48	47.9
6. ResNet50V2	24,607.11	35.7

APPENDIX C

UMAP VISUALIZATION OF SINGLE SLICE CLASSIFICATION TEST SETS

Figure C.1: UMAP Visualization for COVID Class Covering All Datasets.

Figure C.2: UMAP Visualization for NONCOVID Class Covering All Datasets.

Figure C.3: UMAP Visualization for COVID(*red*) and NONCOVID(*gray*) Classes for Each Dataset.

APPENDIX D

COMPLETE AVERAGED GRAD-CAM RESULTS

(a) TP

(b) FN

(c) FP

(d) TN

Figure D.1: Averaged Grad-CAM Results Covering TP, FN, TN, and FP for Single Slice Classification.

